

ANTICANCER ACTIVITY OF *MORUS* (MULBERRY) SPECIES WITH SPECIAL FOCUS ON MORUSIN

Abdullatif Azab*

Eastern Plants Company, Box 868, Arara, Israel, 30025.

Article Received on 15 April 2026,
Article Revised on 05 May 2026,
Article Published on 16 May 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20200843>

*Corresponding Author

Abdullatif Azab

Eastern Plants Company, Box 868,
Arara, Israel, 30025.

How to cite this Article: Abdullatif Azab*. (2026). Anticancer Activity of *Morus* (Mulberry) Species with Special Focus on Morusin. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(10), 322–373.
This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

In our three previous review articles about the *Morus* (mulberry) plant genus, we presented the antidiabetic, brain-related and anti-inflammatory properties-activities of its trees. In this article, anticancer and related activities of this genus will be reviewed. Literature data possess dozens of research articles about this crucial activity, since cancer is one of the major human death causes. Like in our three previous review articles about this genus, *Morus alba* (white mulberry) is the most studied and published. Also, the unique natural products that these plants contain and most of them were previously presented, will be shown in this article. Some of these, reportedly most active, will be presented separately in the discussion section. Species that were not published for anticancer activity will be highlighted in order to raise the need

for research. Finally, we will present the few review articles that were published about anticancer activity of the entire *Morus* genus and show their strengths and weaknesses.

KEYWORDS: Anticancer, *Morus*, *Morus alba*, *Morus nigra*, *Morus indica*, flavonoids, Morusin, Kuwanon, Sanggenon, Nanoparticles.

Abbreviations: DCM dichloromethane, DEE diethyl ether, DMSO dimethyl sulfoxide, DNJ 1-Deoxynojirimycin, EC₅₀ median effective concentration, EO essential oil, EtOAc ethyl acetate, GCC general chemical composition, HPLC high performance liquid chromatography, LPS lipopolysaccharide, NPs nanoparticles, PE petroleum ether, STZ streptozotocin, TAC total antioxidant capacity, TFC total flavonoid content, TPC total phenolic content.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cancer is the second reason of disease-mortality among humans after cardiovascular diseases: around M10 deaths, globally.^[1,2] It is estimated that from 2020 to 2050 this disease, its complications, research and consequences will cost an unbelievable price of 25.2 trillion US dollars.^[3] Between 2016 and 2023, cancer research global funding was an enormous number of 51.4 billion US dollars.^[4]

The anticancer property of the *Morus* plant genus is extensively studied, and it was documented and published in several review articles. Surprisingly, and to the best of our literature search, no significant review articles about anticancer and related activities of the whole genus were published so far. We found four review articles about the anticancer activity of *Morus alba*^[5-8] and one about *Morus nigra*.^[9] For this reason, our review article is the most comprehensive.

2. Published Anticancer Activity of *Morus* Species

Morus genus plants were used by humans since the dawn of humanity for many purposes, nutritional, traditional medicine, industry and energy source. However, there is very little documentation of such use for prevention or treatment of cancer in ethnomedicine, where we found only one reliable publication.^[10] Contrary to that, modern science has widely investigated the medicinal-biological and other properties-activities of these plants and thousands of articles were published. As for anticancer activity, a summary of these findings is presented as follows: ***Morus* Species; Anticancer and Other Activities, Method, Results, Reference**

Morus alba

Cortex methanolic extract had weak activity against cancer-cells injected mice. Fifteen other plants were tested in this research.^[11]

Cortex aqueous extract had moderate activity against K-562, B380 human leukemia cells and B16 mouse melanoma cells. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[12]

Anthocyanins-rich fruits methanolic extract was active against B16-F1 melanoma cells. Four compounds were identified in the extract: two derivatives of Cyanidin and two of Pelargonidin (**Figure 1A**).^[13]

Leaves were separately extracted with *n*-butanol, methanol, 50% aqueous methanol* and

water. The extracts had significant activity against HepG2 cancer cells. A mechanism of action is proposed. Antioxidant activity and TPC are reported.^[14]

* Unless stated otherwise, percentages of solvent mixtures are V/V.

Branches, fruits, leaves and roots were separately extracted with water, and the resulting extracts were fractionized with *n*-hexane, EtOAc and methanol. The methanolic fractions were tested for anticancer activity against Calu-6 cells. The crude extracts were analyzed for organic acids resulting previously well known compounds and phosphoric acid.^[15]

Roots 80% aqueous ethanolic extract had notable activity against multidrug-resistant MCF-7/Dox cancer cells. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[16]

Leaves 70% aqueous methanolic extract was active against colon (HCT-15) and breast (MCF-7) human cancer cells. Mechanism of action based on downregulation of nitric oxide produced by inducible NO-synthase. The extract was chromatographed (HPLC) resulting nine previously known phenolics.^[17]

Roots 70% aqueous ethanolic extract was active against neuroblastoma (B103) cells. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[18]

Leaves 95% aqueous ethanolic extract ameliorated DMBA (7,12-Dimethylbenz(a)anthracene)-induced cancer in *Mesocricetus auratus* (Syrian hamster).^[19], see references]

Leaves aqueous extract inhibited *N*-Nitrosodiethylamine-induced liver cancer in rats.^[20]

Leaves and 30% aqueous ethanol were used to prepare flavonoid-rich extract, and this had cytotoxic effect on HeLa cell lines.^[21]

Leaves ethanolic extract was active against HCT-16 (colon cancer) cells. Antimicrobial activity is also reported.^[22]

Root bark DCM extract was active against H1299, H460, and A549 cell lines. Mechanism of action is proposed, and activity is referred to Morusin (**Figure 1A**) that was detected (HPLC) in the extract.^[23]

Leaves methanolic poly phenols-rich extract was active against Doxorubicin-resistant cancer

cells (liver, three types) which was induced by endoplasmic reticulum stress. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[24]

Leaves were extracted with 80% aqueous ethanol, and the extract was chromatographed obtaining Isoquercetin and Rutin. The crude extract and the two compounds were tested separately and in combination with Cisplatin, against human gastric cancer cells (IBRCC10071). Results showed clear synergism between natural products and the drug.^[25]

Root bark DCM extract was tested against four cell lines (H1299, HCT116, RAW264.7, THP-1) showing significant activity. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[26,27,31]

Leaves and branches were separately extracted with 95% aqueous ethanol, and the extracts had moderate activity against four cancer cell lines. A mechanism of action is proposed; antioxidant activity is presented and *Peganum harmala* (highest activity) and *Melia azedarach* were also tested in this research.^[28]

Fruits aqueous extract inhibited liver fibrosis in rats via suppression of inflammatory biomarkers. Authors concluded that their results indicate possible use against hepatocarcinogenesis.^[29]

Leaves were exposed to γ -radiation then extracted with methanol. The resulting extract had activity against human colorectal HCT116 cancer cells. Grape leaves and seeds extracts were also studied in this research, and antioxidant activity is published.^[30]

Leaves powder was administered to mice resulting significant prevention of liver cancer (STZ-induced).^[32]

Ripe fruits and young leaves were separately extracted with aqueous solutions of 70% methanol, 60% ethanol and 65% acetone (6 extracts). These extracts were tested against MCF-7 breast cancer cells, resulting clear dependence on extracting solvent.^[33]

Leaves and root bark were separately extracted with 80% aqueous methanol and both extracts were tested against U937 human leukemic monocytic cell line: root bark extract was more potent. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[34]

Leaves were separately extracted with DCM and ethanol, and both extracts were tested against HuCCA-1, MCF-7 and A-549 cells: DCM extract was more active. Authors also

tested the activity of an active compound present in these extracts: Chlorogenic acid (higher content in ethanolic extract).^[35]

Nanoemulsion prepared from fruits and leaves (separately) methanolic extracts had notable activity against MCF-7 cancer cells. Major components of fruits extract were fatty acids, while major components of leaves extract were phytosterols.^[36]

Leaves 80% aqueous ethanolic extract had significant activity against HCT-116 cancer cells. Activity was dose and time dependent.^[37,38]

Ripe and unripe fruits were separately extracted with 90% aqueous methanol, and both extracts were tested against A549 lung cancer cells: ripe fruits were more effective. GCC, TPC and antioxidant activities are presented.^[39]

Fruits anthocyanin-rich methanolic extract was active against *N*-Nitrosodiethylamine-induced hepatocarcinogenesis in rats. Effect was verified using several biomarkers and physical parameters. The major component of the extract was Pelargonidin 3-glucoside. Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities are also presented.^[40]

Fruits anthocyanin-rich 95% aqueous ethanolic extract was active against thyroid cancer cells: SW1736 and HTh-7. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[41]

Root bark was extracted with 75% aqueous ethanol, and the extract was fractionized using several solvents, then chromatographed, affording two new and seven previously known compounds (**Figure 1A**): Alfafuran, Dioxycudraflavone A (new), 5-Hydroxyethyl moracin (new), Licoflavone C, Moracin C, Morusignin L, Morusin, Mulberrofuran G and Sanggenon V. All compounds were tested against human lung cancer cell lines (A549 and NCI-H292), but only Morusin and Mulberrofuran were active. Antidiabetic activity is published.^[43]

Three donated prenylated flavonoids, Kuwanon E, Cudraflavone B, and 4'-*O*-Methylkuwanon E (**Figure 1A**), were active against THP-1 cancer cells. Antidiabetic and anti-inflammatory activities are also presented.^[44]

Root bark 80% aqueous ethanolic extract was active against RAW264.7 macrophages and human colorectal cancer cell line SW480. Anti-inflammatory activity is reported.^[45]

Leaves tea and fermented leaves drink were active against HeLa and MCF-7 cancer cells.

Antioxidant activity is reported.^[46]

Stem bark methanolic extract was partitioned with several solvents including EtOAc, and this fraction was tested against Ehrlich's ascites carcinoma cell-induced in mice. Effect was measured using several biomarkers. Antioxidant activity and antioxidative parameters are also published.^[47]

Stem ethanolic extract was active against WiDr cancer cells. Antioxidant activity and GCC are also reported.^[48]

Leaves hot water (95 °C) extract combined with its major component, Neochlorogenic acid (**Figure 1B**), were active against A7r5 cancer cells. Oxidative stress and diabetic conditions were induced by Glucolipototoxicity. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[49]

Leaves 95% aqueous ethanolic extract was active against 7,12-dimethylbenz-anthracene-induced carcinoma in the buccal pouch of Syrian hamster, *Mesocricetus auratus*.^[50]

Leaves 70% aqueous ethanolic flavonoid-rich extract had synergistic effect with Doxorubicin against HT-29 or A-172 GBM cancer cells.^[51,52]

Roots hard wood was successively extracted with *n*-hexane, EtOAc and 70% aqueous acetone. The EtOAc extract was chromatographed affording a new prenylated flavonoid: 7, 2', 4', 6'-Tetrahydroxy-6-geranylflavanone (**Figure 1B**). This compound was active against liver cancer cells (dRLh84).^[53]

Leaves ethanolic extract was analyzed affording nine compounds (**Figure 1B**): Mulberrofuran F1 (new), Mulberrofuran F, Chalcomoracin, Kuwanon J, Morachalcone A, Isobavachalcone, Norartocarpetin, Kuwanon C and 6-Geranylapigenin (Albanin D). The first three compounds were active against A549, Be17402, BGC823, HCT-8 and A2780 cell lines.^[54]

Leaves 70% aqueous ethanolic flavonoid-rich extract was active LL2-cells-induced cancer in mice and DNA (calf) repairing activity.^[55]

Fruits 70% aqueous ethanolic extract was partitioned several times, with several solvents, then its *n*-butanol fraction was chromatographed affording 3S-(β-D-Glucopyranosyloxy)-2,3-

dihydro-2-oxo-1H-indole-3-acetic acid butyl ester (compound 1), its free acid (**Figure 1B**) and five previously known compounds. Compound 1 had activity against HeLa human cancer cells. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[56]

Root bark 80% aqueous ethanolic extract was chromatographed yielding Kuwanon M (**Figure 1C**), where this compound was active against A549 and NCI-H292 cancer cell lines. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[57]

Lectin that was isolated from leaves was active against MCF-7 (human breast cancer) and HCT-15 (colon cancer) cells. Effect was measured with several parameters. In the third article, a mechanism of action is proposed.^[58,59,60]

Donated 4'-*O*-methylkuwanon E (**Figure 1C**) induced differentiation of THP-1 human monocytic leukemia cells and authors concluded that it is potential cyto-differentiating anticancer agent.^[61]

Commercial Morusin was active against DU145, PC3, LNCaP and RWPE-1 cell lines. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[62]

Follow-up of previous research using MCF-7, MDA-MB-231, MDA-MB-157, MDA-MB-453 and MCF10A cell lines. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[63]

Follow-up of previous research using H1299, H292, and H460 cell lines. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[64]

Mulberroside A (**Figure 1C**) was isolated from 95% aqueous ethanolic extract of twigs and branches (*Ramulus Mori*), and it had positive effect in HepA tumor-bearing mice.^[65]

Fruits aqueous extract had synergistic effect with Paclitaxel against TSGH 8301 human bladder cancer cell line. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[66]

Root bark was extracted with water, fractionized with ethanol and chromatographed affording three polysaccharides. These were analyzed for monosaccharides composition, structure and tested against SMMC7721 liver cancer cells, where one of them was active.^[67]

Cortex was extracted with methanol, partitioned with EtOAc and chromatographed yielding Sanggenon G (**Figure 1C**), which was active against MDA-MB231 cell line.^[68]

Twenty-eight (28) commercially available compounds from this species were tested against melanoma cells *in vitro*. Eleven compounds were active, and most potent was Sanggenon C (**Figure 1C**). A mechanism of action is proposed.^[69]

Fruits 80% aqueous ethanolic flavonoid-rich extract had positive effect against colorectal tumorigenesis in mice. An extensive anti-inflammatory study is also reported.^[70]

Root bark was separately extracted with water and 70% aqueous ethanol. Both extracts were tested and found active against LPS-induced proliferation in splenocytes isolated from mice. Anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities are reported.^[71]

Root bark 70% aqueous ethanolic extract was active against HeLa, HepG2 and NCI-H460 cell lines. Detailed extraction methods, TPC, antioxidant, antihyperlipidemic and three enzymes inhibition, are also reported.^[72]

Raw leaves, fermented leaves, roots, branches and fruits were separately extracted with 95% aqueous methanol. The extracts were tested against HCT-116, SNU-601, Calu-6 and MCF-7 cell lines. A range of potency is reported for each extract and each cell line. Antioxidant activity and TPC are reported.^[73]

Fruits were extracted with four solvent mixtures each containing 0.1% acetic acid to ensure flavonoid-rich products: water, 75% aqueous methanol/ethanol/acetone. The four extracts were tested against proliferation of HepG2 cells, resulting EC₅₀ (mg/mL) 56.8, 37.8, 34.75 and 28.3, respectively.^[74]

Leaves were separately extracted with water, methanol and 50% aqueous methanol. The extracts were tested against human hepatocellular carcinoma HepG2 cell line. Effect was measured with several parameters, especially cell viability, where 100% methanolic extract was most effective.^[75]

Leaves were extracted with 95% aqueous ethanol, partitioned with EtOAc and methanol, and the methanolic fraction was chromatographed affording 13 compounds, one of them was new: (2*S*)-4'-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-8-prenylflavan (**Figure 1C**). All thirteen compounds were tested for inhibition of proliferation and differentiation of 3T3-L1 preadipocytes. Three known compounds were active: 2',7-Dihydroxy-4'-methoxy-8-prenylflavan, Morachalcone B (**Figure 1C**) and Isobavachalcone.^[76]

Leaves 80% aqueous methanolic extract showed highest activity among four tested plants, against P19 embryonal carcinoma cells.^[77]

Leaves were separately extracted with water, 80% aqueous methanol and 70% aqueous ethanol. These extracts were tested against human breast cancer cell lines, MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231, where the three extracts had almost equal average activities. The antioxidant activity of the extracts is also published. The ethanolic extract was partially analyzed for chemical composition yielding eight known compounds including 1-Deoxynojirimycin (1-DNJ, **Figure 1C**).^[78]

Root bark 75% aqueous ethanolic extract was partitioned with several solvents including *n*-butanol. This fraction was chromatographed affording 5,2'-dihydroxyflavanone-7,4'-di-*O*- β -*D*-glucoside (**Figure 1C**). This compound was active against HO-8910 cells.^[79]

Root bark 80% aqueous ethanolic extract and its component Ursolic acid (**Figure 1D**) were active against multiple myeloma cells (RPMI8226, HEK293, Wnt3a-L). A mechanism of action is proposed.^[80]

Cortex ethanolic extract was partitioned with EtOAc and water, and the organic fraction was analyzed affording Sanggenon C. This compound decreased tumor cells (H22, P388, K562) viability. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[81]

Fruits aqueous extract was active against RAW264.7 and CT26 cell lines, where the effect was verified using several parameters. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[82]

Leaves methanolic extract was partitioned with *n*-hexane and EtOAc, and the EtOAc fraction was chromatographed yielding eleven compounds where 3'-Geranyl-3-prenyl-2',4',5,7-tetrahydroxyflavone (**Figure 1D**) was new. All compounds were tested against three human carcinoma cells (HeLa, MCF-7, Hep3B) but only Morusin was active.^[83]

Root bark methanolic extract was fractionized with water and EtOAc, and the EtOAc fraction was analyzed affording 15 compounds where Soroceal B and Sanggenol Q (**Figure 1D**) were new. All fifteen compounds were tested against HL-60, Hela, HepG-2, A-549 and AGS cell lines. The active compounds: Soroceal B, Sanggenol, Morusinol (**Figure 1D**); in addition to Mulberrofuran G, Mongolicin (not indicated which), Licoflavone C, Morusin and 3'-Geranyl-3-prenyl-2',4',5,7-tetrahydroxyflavone. Anti-inflammatory activity is reported.^[84]

Leaves 95% aqueous ethanolic extracts was analyzed yielding Morachalcone C (**Figure 1D**) and Morachalcone B. Both compounds had moderate activity against HCT-8 and BGC823 human cancer cell lines.^[85]

Root bark methanolic extract was fractionized with several solvents including EtOAc, and this fraction was chromatographed affording Albanol A and Mulberrofuran Q (**Figure 1D**). Albanol A was more active against human leukemia (HL60) and human melanoma (CRL1579) cell lines than Mulberrofuran Q.^[86]

Root bark methanolic extract was fractionized with several solvents including EtOAc, and this fraction was chromatographed affording Albanol B (**Figure 1D**). This compound was active against human lung cancer cell lines (A549, BZR, H1975, H226) and tumor growth in Ex-3LL (Lewis lung carcinoma) tumor-bearing mice. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[87]

Cyanidin-3-glucoside was isolated from fruits had inhibition effect on human breast cancer cell line, MDA-MB-453 inoculated in mice. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[88]

Feeding mice 1-DNJ prevented Azoxymethane-induced colorectal cancer in mice. Effect was measured using several parameters.^[89]

Donated Guangsangon E (**Figure 1E**) isolated from leaves, inhibited cell proliferation and induces apoptosis in A549 and CNE1 cells and tumor in mice after injection these cells in the animals. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[90]

Commercial Kuwanon A (**Figure 1E**) had synergistic action with 5-Fluorouracil against gastric cancer cells (MKN-45, SGC-7901, HGC-27, BGC-823) and against gastric cancer in mice. Effect was measured with several biomarkers, and a mechanism of action is proposed.^[91]

Commercial Kuwanon C was more active against HeLa cancer cells, compared with other natural products (commercial) found in different parts of this tree, and were used in this study. Effect was measured with several biomarkers, and a mechanism of action is proposed.^[92]

Morusin was isolated from the methanolic extract of root bark, inhibited 12-*O*-tetradecanoylphorbol-13-acetate- (TPA) and 7,12-Dimethylbenz(*a*)anthracene-induced

carcinogenesis in mice. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[93]

Morusin was isolated from the ethanolic extract of branches bark (*Ramulus mori*), inhibited transplanted H₂₂ hepatocarcinoma in mice.^[94]

Morusin was isolated from the ethanolic extract of branches bark (*Ramulus mori*), inhibited Bel-7402 cells. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[95]

Commercial Morusin was active against human hepatocarcinoma cells (HepG2, Hep3B) *in vitro*, and transplanting them in mice, *in vivo*. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[96]

Commercial Morusin suppressed A549 cancer cells. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[97]

Commercial Morusin inhibited human hepatocellular cancer cell lines Hep3B and Huh7. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[98]

Commercial Morusin had *in vitro* activity (against MCF-10A, MCF-7, MDA-MB-231 cancer cells), and *in vivo*, against MCF-7 cancer cells-induced tumor in mice. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[99]

Commercial Morusin inhibited prostate cancer cells: PC-3 and 22Rv1. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[100]

Commercial Morusinol was active against A375, 293FT and MV3 cells. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[101,122]

Commercial Mulberroside A inhibited A498 kidney cancer cells. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[102]

Commercial Sanggenon C inhibited the growth and proliferation of glioblastoma cells. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[103]

Commercial Sanggenon C had *in vitro* activity against A549 lung cancer cells, *in vivo* against tumor induced by the same cells in mice. Molecular docking was conducted. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[104]

Commercial Sanggenon O (**Figure 1E**) inhibited A549 lung cancer cells and a dual action mechanism is proposed.^[105]

Root bark methanolic extract was partitioned with chloroform and chromatographed yielding two new compounds Moracin P and Moracin Q, in addition to Moracin O, Moracin M, Mulberrofuran D, Mulberrofuran H, Mulberrofuran W and Albafuran A (**Figure 1E**); and Mulberrofuran G, Sanggenon O, Sanggenon C. Seven of these compounds, including the new ones, were active against Hep3B carcinoma cells. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[106]

Leaves methanolic extract had weak activity against LNCaP and DU145 prostate cancer cell lines, while stems methanolic extract had significant activity against LNCaP cells and weak activity against DU145 cells.^[107]

Leaves were sequentially extracted with PE, chloroform and methanol. The methanolic extract was tested against Ehrlich ascites tumor in mice, showing significant activity. GCCs of the extract were also determined.^[108]

Leaves were sequentially extracted with PE, chloroform and methanol, and each extract was fractionated with several solvents. The methanolic extract was tested against MCF7 and 3T3 cancer cell lines showing significant effect. This extract was chromatographed affording Cathafuran B (**Figure 1E**), Ursolic acid and Moracin M. These compounds were also tested against the same cancer cells resulting similar effect to the methanolic extract. TFC, TPC and antioxidant activity are also reported.^[109]

Leaves aqueous ethanolic extract (ratio is not indicated) with/without same extract of *M. nigra* were tested for antimutagenic activity in γ -rays irradiated rats and roots of *Vicia faba*, resulting significant positive effect in both cases.^[110]

Fresh fruits 70% aqueous ethanolic extract was tested against HepG2, MCF7, HCT116 and PC3 cancer cell lines, showing moderate to significant effect. The extract was fractionized with *n*-hexane, DCM and EtOAc, and these fractions were chromatographed yielding known compounds, mainly phytosterols and fatty acids. Antioxidant activity of the crude extract is also reported.^[111]

Morus atropurpurea

No published anticancer and its related activities.

Morus australis

Morusin was isolated from roots ethanolic extract and was tested against TPA-induced cancer

in JB6 cells, and after their implantation in mice skin. Antioxidant activity is reported and a mechanism of action is proposed.^[112]

Stem bark 95% aqueous ethanolic extract was partitioned with PE, CHCl₃, EtOAc, acetone, and methanol, successively. The EtOAc fraction was chromatographed yielding three new compounds Australisines A–C, in addition to Mulberrofuran E, Mulberrofuran J, Mongolicin C, Kuwanon G (**Figure 2**), Mulberrofuran F, Mulberrofuran G, Mulberrofuran Q, Chalcomoracin. Australisines A–C, Mulberrofuran G, Mongolicin C, and Chalcomoracin showed moderate cytotoxic activities against five human cancer cell lines (A549, Bel 7402, BGC 823, HCT-8, A2780).^[113]

Morus bombycis

Root bark methanolic extract was partitioned with chloroform and chromatographed yielding Kuwanon Q, Kuwanon R, Kuwanon V (**Figure 3**) and Kuwanon J. These compounds were tested against Hep3B carcinoma cells, and only Kuwanon J was active. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[106]

Leaves methanolic extract had weak activity against LNCaP and DU145 prostate cancer cell lines.^[107]

Root bark methanolic extract was analyzed affording Kuwanon H (**Figure 3**) and Kuwanon G. These compounds inhibited specific binding of gastrin-releasing peptide (GRP) to GRP-preferring receptors in murine Swiss 3T3 fibroblasts.^[114]

Morus cathayana

Leaves methanolic extract had weak activity against LNCaP and no activity against DU145 prostate cancer cell lines. In the article, this species is referred to as *Morus tiliaefolia*.^[107]

Root bark 95% aqueous ethanolic extract was partitioned with CHCl₃ and EtOAc successively. The EtOAc fraction was chromatographed yielding two new compounds Cathayanons A and B (**Figure 4**). These compounds inhibited human leukemia HL-60 cells.^[115]

Morus celtidifolia

Leaves were successively extracted with *n*-hexane and methanol, and the resulting extracts were tested against MCF-7 and HeLa cancer cell lines, showing moderate activities.

Antimicrobial and antioxidant activities are also reported.^[116]

Morus ihou

No published anticancer and its related activities.

Morus indica

Leaves were successively extracted with PE, benzene, EtOAc, acetone, methanol and water. The methanolic extract was active against TPA- and DMBA-induced two-stage cancer in mice skin (*in vivo*). *In vitro* tests included inhibition of the activity and level of aryl hydrocarbon hydroxylase. The effect was measured using several biomarkers and a mechanism of action is proposed.^[117]

Leaves of two varieties were separately extracted with ethanol, methanol and water. The extracts were tested against HT-29 cancer cells showing moderate effects. GCCs and antioxidant activities are also reported.^[118]

Morus isingnis

No published anticancer and its related activities.

Morus japonica

No published anticancer and its related activities.

Morus laevigata

Leaves were sequentially extracted with PE, chloroform and methanol. The methanolic extract was tested against Ehrlich ascites tumor in mice, showing significant activity. GCCs of the extract were also determined.^[108]

Leaves were sequentially extracted with PE, chloroform and methanol, and each extract was fractionated with several solvents. The methanolic extract was tested against MCF7 and 3T3 cancer cell lines showing significant effect. TFC, TPC and antioxidant activity are also reported.^[109]

Morus latifolia

Bark and leaves were separately extracted with methanol, and the resulting extract were active against Ehrlich's ascites carcinoma in mice. The effect was measured using several parameters. Antioxidant activity is also reported.^[119]

Morus liboensis

No published anticancer and its related activities.

Morus macroura

Cultured hairy roots methanolic extract was chromatographed yielding three Diels-Alder type adducts: Sorocein I (**Figure 5**), Chalcomoracin and Guangsangon E. The three compounds were tested against P-388 murine leukemia cell line, but only Guangsangon E was active.^[120]

Fruits, leaves and stems were separately extracted with 80% aqueous ethanol, and the resulting extracts were partitioned with PE, DCM and EtOAc. The EtOAc fractions were analyzed affording seven previously known phenolics. These were tested against HepG-2, MCF-7, and HeLa cancer cell lines, where kaempferol-3-O- β -glucoside and quercetin-3-O- β -glucoside were found potent. Molecular docking was performed, and neuroprotective activity is also reported.^[121]

Morus mesozygia

Stem bark methanolic extract was fractionated and chromatographed affording Artocarpesin, Artochamin C, Kushenol E and Moracin L (**Figure 6**), in addition to Moracin M, Moracin C and Mulberrofuran F. The crude extract and the seven isolated compounds were active against MCF-7 cancer cells, where Moracin L was most active. Structure activity relationship and antiparasitic activity are presented.^[123]

Morus mongolica

Molecular docking was performed for four previously known phenolics that were isolated from this species, revealing potential of DEK oncoprotein inhibition activity.^[124]

Root bark 95% aqueous ethanolic extract was partitioned with DEE and chromatographed yielding six new (2001) compounds, Sanggenol L, Sanggenol M, Mulberrofuran X, Mulberrofuran Y, Mulberrofuran Z (**Figure 7**), Mulberrofuran W, along with 10 known flavonoids. All compounds were tested and found against human oral tumor cell lines (HSC-2 and HSG), ranging from moderate to high activities.^[125]

Morus multicaulis

No published anticancer and its related activities.

Morus nigra

Leaves aqueous ethanolic extract (ratio is not indicated) with/without same extract of *M. alba* were tested for antimutagenic activity in γ -rays irradiated rats and roots of *Vicia faba*, resulting significant positive effect in both cases.^[110]

Leaves *n*-hexane and 70% aqueous methanolic extract were active against human cervical cancer cell line (HeLa).^[126]

Fresh and dry fruits were separately extracted with 70% aqueous ethanol. The extracts was active against human breast cancer cell line (MCF-7), where the extract of the fresh fruits was more active. The effect was measured using several parameters.^[127]

Fruits 80% aqueous methanolic extract was chromatographed affording leptin Morniga G and one of its components Chalcone 4 hydrate (**Figure 8**). The crude extract and its isolated ingredients were active against human colorectal adenocarcinoma cells, HT-29. The effect was measured using several parameters.^[128]

Fruits juice had protective activity against genomic changes in human lymphocytes. Juice was analyzed for phenolics yielding 14 known compounds. TAC is also reported.^[129]

Eleven new genotypes fruits were extracted with ethanol, and the extracts were active against MCF-7 cancer cell line. The fruits were analyzed for several general components, and their antioxidant capacities were determined. Same analysis was conducted for heartwood.^[130]

Fruits 50% aqueous ethanolic anthocyanin-rich prolonged life of Diethylnitrosamine-induced hepatocellular carcinoma rats. The effect was measured using several parameters. The major components of the extract were (mg/g): Peonidin-3-glucoside 20.3 (**Figure 8**), Cyanidin-3-glucoside 14.7, Malvidin-3-glucoside 14.1 and Delphinidin-3-glucoside 11.3.^[131]

Fruits juice was active against human breast cancer (MDA-MB-231) and prostate cancer (PC3) cell lines, in a dose dependant manner.^[132]

Sour fruits 80% aqueous ethanolic extract was active against human colon cancer HT-29 cells. A mechanism of action is proposed. Antioxidant activity is reported.^[133]

Leaves of *Morus nigra* and *Ocimum basilicum* and their mixture were separately extracted using *n*-hexane, chloroform, EtOAc and methanol. The extracts (12) were tested against

MDA-MB-231, MCF-7, HepG2, Huh-7, LoVo and HCT116 cancer cell lines. Results showed clear advantage of the combination and synergistic effect. The antioxidant activity of the combined extracts and their partial chemical compositions are also reported.^[134]

Fruits were separately extracted with water and 75% aqueous ethanol, then the resulting extract were treated with high temperature for solvent removal. This resulted in decrease of anthocyanin but increase of TPC. Activity of HCT-116 cells inhibition was higher for heated extracts. Antioxidant activity is also reported.^[135]

Fruits 95% aqueous ethanolic extract was analyzed resulting the isolation of twenty compounds, including two new: Moranigrine A and Morusamine (**Figure 8**). All isolated compounds were tested for inhibition of 3-Phosphoglycerate dehydrogenase, where Methyl caffeate (**Figure 8**) exhibited effective inhibition effect. Molecular docking is reported.^[136]

Exosome-like lipid nanoparticles were isolated from leaves, and they were rich in glycolipids, functional proteins, and active small active molecules. The were tested *in vitro* against HepG2, CT-26, Hepal-6, 4T1, A549, L929, and MC3T3-E1 cells; and *in vivo* against Diethylnitrosamine-induced cancer in mice. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[137]

Fruits DMSO extract was active against human prostate adenocarcinoma (PC-3) cells. TPC and antioxidant activity of the extract are reported.^[138]

Fruits anthocyanin-rich methanolic extract was active against HeLa and A2780 cancer cell lines. The phenolics composition of the extract is presented.^[42]

Stem bark methanolic was partitioned with several solvents including EtOAc, and this fraction was chromatographed affording 15 compounds: 2',3,4',5,5'-Pentahydroxy-*cis*-stilbene, Resveratrol, Oxyresveratrol, Albufuran C, 3-Acetyl-*O*- α -amyrin, 3-Acetyl-*O*- β -amyrin and Uvaol (**Figure 8**), in addition to Norartocarpetin, Kuwanon C, Morusin, Cudraflavone A, Kuwanon G, Mulberrofuran G, Ursolic acid-3-*O*-acetate. Five derivatives (methylated) were prepared from the first listed three compounds, and all 19 compounds were tested against HepG2 and MCF-7 cell lines. One of these derivatives (shown in **Figure 8** as "Active Derivative") and Kuwanon C showed highest activities.^[139]

Heartwood methanolic was partitioned with several solvents including EtOAc, and this fraction was chromatographed affording two compounds that were reported for the first time

from this species: Norartocarpanone and Euchrenone a7 (**Figure 8**). Both compounds were tested against P-388 leukemia cells, where Euchrenone a7 was more cytotoxic than Norartocarpanone, and their IC₅₀ were 7.8 and 12.7 µg/mL respectively.^[140]

Morus notabilis

No published anticancer and its related activities.

Morus papyrifera

No published anticancer and its related activities.

Morus rotundiloba

Leaves EO (hydrodistillation) had activity against Hep2 and SW620 cell lines. The reported major component of this EO (10.48%) is Benzyl alcohol. Antimicrobial and antiviral activities are also reported.^[141]

Leaves hot aqueous extract was fractionized with DEE and this fraction was analyzed yielding six identified compounds, where the three major components were (**Figure 9**, %): Tannic acid 37.9, Epigallocatechin-3-*O*-gallate 21.1 and Caffeic acid 11.2. The DEE fraction was active against mutagenic *Salmonella typhimurium* strain TA 98 induced by a mutagen Trp-P-1. Antiviral activity is also reported.^[142]

Morus rubra

Fresh fruits 70% aqueous ethanolic extract was tested against HepG2, MCF7, HCT116 and PC3 cancer cell lines, showing moderate to significant effect. The extract was fractionized with *n*-hexane, DCM and EtOAc, and these fractions were chromatographed yielding known compounds, mainly phytosterols and fatty acids. Antioxidant activity of the crude extract is also reported.^[111]

Fruits DMSO extract was active against human colon cancer (WiDr) cells. The effect was measured using several parameters and a mechanism of action is proposed.^[143]

Phenolics-rich fruits DMSO extract was active against human prostate (PC-3) and lung (A549) cancer cells, with human normal foreskin fibroblast (CRL-2522) cells and Cisplatin as references. The extract was analyzed resulting the isolation of seven known phenolics. TPC and antioxidant capacity are also reported.^[144]

Morus serrata

Leaves were sequentially extracted with PE, chloroform and methanol, and each extract was fractionated with several solvents. The methanolic extract was tested against MCF7 and 3T3 cancer cell lines showing significant effect. TFC, TPC and antioxidant activity are also reported.^[109]

Morus trilobata

No published anticancer and its related activities.

Morus wittiorum

Stem bark 95% aqueous ethanolic extract was fractionized with PE, CHCl₃ and EtOAc, and this fraction was chromatographed affording nine known compounds: 4'-Prenyloxyresveratrol (**Figure 10A**) Quercetin, 5,7,3',4'-Tetrahydroxy-3-methoxyflavone, Norartocarpanone, Dihydrokaempferol, Euchrenone a7, Morachalcone A, Resveratrol and Oxyresveratrol. These compounds were tested against human ovarian cancer (A2780) and human gastric cancer (BGC-823), where two of them were active. Anti-inflammatory activity is also reported.^[145]

Follow up of previous research yielded three new compounds: Wittifuran H, Wittifuran I and Wittifuran U (**Figure 10A**). These compounds were tested against human gastric cancer cell line BGC-823, but only Wittifuran I was active. Anti-inflammatory activity is reported.^[146]

Another study by the same group of previous two publications with the same isolation methods. In this study, four new compounds were isolated, Wittiorumin G, Wittifurans P–R, along with Sorocein A, Mulberrofuran O (**Figure 10A**) Albafuran C, Mulberrofuran E, Mulberrofuran F. These compounds were tested and some of them were active against five human cancer cell lines (A549, Bel-7402, BGC-823, HCT-8, A2780). Antioxidant activity is reported.^[147]

Fourth research by the same group using same methods resulted the isolation of Wittifurans O, N, K and L (**Figure 10B**). These compounds were tested against human ovarian cancer cell line A2780, but only the first two were active.^[148]

Morus yunnanensis

No published anticancer and its related activities.

Figure 1AL Natural products isolated from *Morus alba*.

Figure 1B: Natural products isolated from *Morus alba*.

Figure 1C: Natural products isolated from *Morus alba*.

Figure 1D: Natural products isolated from *Morus alba*.

Figure 1E: Natural products isolated from *Morus alba*.

Figure 2: Natural products isolated from *Morus australis*.

Figure 3: Natural products isolated from *Morus bombycis*.

Figure 4: Natural products isolated from *Morus cathayana*.

Figure 5: Natural products isolated from *Morus macrourea*.

Figure 6: Natural products isolated from *Morus*.

Figure 7: Natural products isolated from *Morus mongolica*.

Figure 8: Natural products isolated from *Morus nigra*.

Figure 9: Natural products isolated from *Morus rotundiloba*.

Figure 10A: Natural products isolated from *Morus wittiorum*.

Figure 10B: Natural products isolated from *Morus wittiorum*.

3. DISCUSSION

In our previous three articles about the medicinal activities of *Morus* genus we reviewed the nutritive and antidiabetic^[149], the brain-related protective^[150], and the anti-inflammatory properties.^[151] Based on the rich literature data of anticancer activity publications of this genus, this review article is the fourth out of five in this series, where the last will be about antioxidant activity. In this discussion, special attention is given to the very active natural product Morusin.

But as we mentioned in the introduction (section 1), review articles about the anticancer activity were published per species, and the whole *Morus* genus was not published in significant articles. Contrary to that, Morusin (see below) and a few other natural products were reviewed and published. A.H. Pratama *et al.* reviewed the possible potential of Morin (**Figure 11**), isolated from *Morus alba*, as anti-breast-cancer agent.^[152]

Figure 11: The structure of Morin (Flavonol).

Due to the extensive influence of the extraction method on the quantity and the quality of its

outcome, especially its natural products composition, many studies were conducted to optimize this process. In the previous section we cited the works of F. Li *ahc*^[74] and A.K. Srivastava *ahc*.^[81] But these efforts are continuous and S. Fenderya *ahc* carried out extractions with ethanol-water mixtures, where some of them were ultrasound assisted, and others were not.^[153] They discovered that the use of ultrasound assistance did not improve the anticancer activity of the extract, against Caco-2 cells.

Three of the publications that we encountered during the writing of this review article were of special interest. We cited N.T. Dat *ahc* that reported 3'-Geranyl-3-prenyl-2',4',5,7-tetrahydroxyflavone (**Figure 1D**) was new but inactive anticancer compound^[83]. This finding contradicts the results of J. Qin *ahc* that reported that this compound was active anticancer agent.^[84] S.R. Deshmukh *ahc* reported the antioxidant and antiproliferative activities of the plant commonly known as Noni or Indian Mulberry.^[154] In fact, this plant does not belong to the *Morus* genus and not even to the Moraceae family. Its scientific name is *Morinda citrifolia*, it is part of the *Morinda* genus, which is part of the Rubiaceae (Coffee) family. But it is very important to notice the very close appearance of its fruits and leaves to those of *Morus alba*.

Numerous research and review articles were published about the preparation of nanoparticles (NPs) using *Morus* extracts, and the uses of these NPs for various, mainly medicinal purposes. For example, M.F. Baran *ahc* prepared silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) using *Morus alba* leaves extract, and these NPs were active against aging-related infectious diseases.^[155] R. Nazario-Naveda *ahc* also synthesized AgNPs using *Morus nigra* fruits, and the resulting NPs were highly active against two bacterial strains.^[156]

But in this article will focus on NPs with anticancer and related activities. Summary of the published articles is presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1: NPs with anticancer activity, prepared using *Morus* materials.

NPs	<i>Morus</i> Species	Testing Method [Reference]
Ag	<i>alba</i>	Potato disc assay ^[157]
Ag	<i>alba</i>	Against MCF-7 and MCF-10A cells ^[158]
Ag	<i>alba</i>	Against MCF-7 cells ^[159]
Ag	<i>indica</i>	Against HT-29 cells ^[160]
Ag	<i>indica</i>	Against HepG2 cells ^[161]
Ag	<i>nigra</i>	Against MCF-7 cells ^[162]
Ag/Cu	<i>nigra</i>	Against HeLa and HCT116 cells ^[163]

Ag/ZnO/Ag-ZnO	<i>macrourea</i>	Against HepG2 cells ^[164]
Au	<i>nigra</i>	Against MCF-7, HT-29, OVCAR3, HeLa cells ^[165]
Se	<i>rubra</i>	Against MDA-MB-231 cells ^[166]
ZnO	<i>laevigata</i>	Against HT-29 cells ^[167]
ZnO	<i>nigra</i>	Against AGS gastric cancer cells ^[168]

Of all the compounds isolated from *Morus* species, Morusin (**Figure 1A**) was the most studied, most published and most mentioned in this article. Its studies were so extensive and frequent, so it was published in many research articles, but also in review articles. For this part of our review article, we will cite more publications that are related to this natural product, which were not cited above. These publications will be summarized in **Table 2** below.

Table 2: Additional Publication about Morusin (References 1-168 are not included).

Author(s)	Article Type	Major Topic(s), Reference
S.W. Cho ahc	Research	The roles of Morusin and autophagy in possible anticancer activity ^[169]
S. Agarwal ahc	Research	Morusin loaded niosomes for cancer therapy ^[170]
H.J. Park & S.H. Park	Research	Mechanism of action is proposed for cytoprotective autophagy by Morusin ^[171]
J. Wang ahc	Research	Mechanism of action is proposed for autophagy and apoptosis induced by Morusin ^[172]
C. Bailly	Research	Structural relationships of Artonin E and Morusin (see Figure 12) and molecular docking for anticancer activity ^[173]
S. Sarmoko ahc	Research	Theoretical investigation of the mechanisms of action of Morusin as anti-breast cancer, and molecular docking ^[174]
Y. Ran ahc	Research	Morusin-Cu(II)-indocyanine green nano-assembly for chemo-photothermal tumor therapy ^[175]
D.W. Choi ahc	Review	Various activities of Morusin including anticancer. Very illustrative, well organized and informative. Mechanism of action are presented. ^[176]
A. Panek-Krzysko, M. Stompor-Goracy	Review	Effect on human health. Mechanisms of action, <i>Morus</i> sources, metabolites, synthesis, various activities with focus on anticancer. Excellent. ^[177]
A. Hafeez ahc	Review	General activities focusing on anticancer. Very illustrative, mechanisms of action, sources, structurally close compounds. Excellent. ^[178]
M. Fatima ahc	Review	General for bioactive compounds of <i>Morus alba</i> , including Morusin. Very informative for history and number of publications. ^[179]
E.W. Chan	Review	General: chemistry and pharmacological properties of Morusin and Morusinol. ^[180]

Z. Zoofishan ahc	Review	Phenolic antioxidants of <i>Morus nigra</i> roots, and antitumor potential of Morusin. Very rich with natural products structures. ^[181]
H.N. Azzam ahc	Review	Morusin as drug candidate. Short version of the biosynthesis is presented (Figure 13). ^[182]

Figure 12: Structures of Artonin E and Morusin.

Figure 13: The Biosynthesis of Morusin.

Finally, several research groups published successful laboratory synthesis of Morusin. Among these, the work of T.H. Tseng ahc is the most significant.^[183]

4. CONCLUSIONS

1) *Morus* species, especially *Morus alba* possess high anticancer potential.

- 2) While *Morus alba* was extensively studied and published, some other species were very limitedly or not published at all for anticancer activity.
- 3) Based on item 2, significant research efforts are needed.
- 4) *Morus* species contain very active anticancer natural products like Morusin.
- 5) Some other natural products were also investigated for anticancer activity, but the published results indicate that more compounds should be tested.

5. REFERENCES

1. Dattani S, Spooner F, Ritchie H, Roser M. Causes of Death. *Our World in Data*, 2023.
2. Poorolajal J. Neglected Major Causes of Death Much Deadlier Than COVID-19. *J Res Health Sci.*, 2020; 20: e00478. DOI: 10.34172/jrhs.2020.13
3. Chen S, Cao Z, Prettner K, Kuhn M, Yang J, Jiao L, Wang Z, Li W, Geldsetzer P, Bärnighausen T, Bloom DE, Wang C. Estimates and Projections of the Global Economic Cost of 29 Cancers in 204 Countries and Territories From 2020 to 2050. *JAMA Oncol.*, 2023; 9: 465-472. DOI: 10.1001/jamaoncol.2022.7826
4. Du A, Brede M, McIntosh SA, Zhang B, Alem AO, Borin G, Cheah W, Copson E, Cutress RI, Folz A, Helms ET, Memon Z, Olaniran OH, Savva C, Thomas E, Atun R, Head MG. Public and philanthropic research funding, publications, and research networks for cancer in the Commonwealth and globally between 2016 and 2023: a comparative analysis. *Lancet Oncol*, 2025; 26: e466-e476. DOI: 10.1016/S1470-2045(25)00338-9
5. Chan EW, Wong SK, Inoue T, Chan HT. Phenolic constituents from the root bark of *Morus alba* with emphasis on morusin and its anti-cancer properties. *J Chin Pharm Sci.*, 2019; 28: 75-87. DOI: 10.5246/jcps.2019.02.008
6. Chan EW, Wong SK, Tangah J, Inoue T, Chan HT. Phenolic constituents and anticancer properties of *Morus alba* (white mulberry) leaves. *J Integr Med.*, 2020; 18: 189-195. DOI: 10.1016/j.joim.2020.02.006
7. Jan B, Parveen R, Zahiruddin S, Khan MU, Mohapatra S, Ahmad S. Nutritional constituents of mulberry and their potential applications in food and pharmaceuticals: A review. *Saudi J Biol Sci.*, 2021; 28: 3909-3921. DOI: 10.1016/j.sjbs.2021.03.056
8. Srivastava AK, Sunil L, Thulasy G, Doss SG, Singh D. Cutting-edge extraction technologies for anticancer compounds from ethnomedicinal mulberry: A molecular review in cancer management. *Notulae Sci Biol.*, 2025; 17: 12241-12241. DOI: 10.15835/nsb17212241
9. Ferraz AP, Figueiredo PO, Yoshida NC. Black Mulberry (*Morus nigra* L.): A Review of

- Attributes as an Anticancer Agent to Encourage Pharmaceutical Development. *Adv Pharmacol Pharm Sci.*, 2024; 3784092. DOI: 10.1155/2024/3784092
10. Yadav S, Nair N, Biharee A, Prathap VM, Majeed J. Updated ethnobotanical notes, phytochemistry and phytopharmacology of plants belonging to the genus *Morus* (Family: Moraceae). *Phytomed Plus.*, 2022; 2: 100120. DOI: 10.1016/j.phyplu.2021.100120
 11. Chang IM, Woo W.S. Screening of Korean medicinal plants for antitumor activity. *Arch Pharm Res.*, 1980; 3: 75-78. DOI: 10.1007/BF02855806
 12. Nam SY, Yi HK, Lee JC, Kim JC, Song CH, Park JW, Lee DY, Kim JS, Hwang PH. Cortex mori extract induces cancer cell apoptosis through inhibition of microtubule assembly. *Arch Pharm Res.*, 2002; 25: 191-196. DOI: 10.1007/BF02976562
 13. Huang HP, Shih YW, Chang YC, Hung CN, Wang CJ. Chemoinhibitory effect of mulberry anthocyanins on melanoma metastasis involved in the Ras/PI3K pathway. *J Agric Food Chem.*, 2008; 56: 9286-9293. DOI: 10.1021/jf8013102
 14. Naowaratwattana W, De-Eknamkul W, De Mejia EG. Phenolic-containing organic extracts of mulberry (*Morus alba* L.) leaves inhibit HepG2 hepatoma cells through G2/M phase arrest, induction of apoptosis, and inhibition of topoisomerase II α activity. *J Med Food*, 2010; 13: 1045-1056. DOI: 10.1089/jmf.2010.1021
 15. Gug K. Physiological and whitening effects of *Morus alba* extracts. *J Chosun Nat Sci.*, 2012; 5: 46-52. DOI: 10.13160/ricns.2012.5.1.046
 16. Choi YK, Cho SG, Choi HS, Woo SM, Yun YJ, Shin YC, Ko SG. JNK1/2 Activation by an Extract from the Roots of *Morus alba* L. Reduces the Viability of Multidrug-Resistant MCF-7/Dox Cells by Inhibiting YB-1-Dependent MDR1 Expression. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med.*, 2013; 741985. DOI: 10.1155/2013/741985
 17. Deepa M, Sureshkumar T, Satheeshkumar PK, Priya S. Antioxidant rich *Morus alba* leaf extract induces apoptosis in human colon and breast cancer cells by the downregulation of nitric oxide produced by inducible nitric oxide synthase. *Nutr Cancer*, 2013; 65: 305-310. DOI: 10.1080/01635581.2013.748924
 18. Kwon YH, Bishayee K, Rahman A, Hong JS, Lim SS, Huh SO. *Morus alba* Accumulates Reactive Oxygen Species to Initiate Apoptosis via FOXO-Caspase 3-Dependent Pathway in Neuroblastoma Cells. *Mol Cells*, 2015; 38: 630-637. DOI: 10.14348/molcells.2015.0030
 19. Khyade VB, Deshpande SD. Chemopreventive efficacy of Ethanolic Extractives of leaves of Mulberry, *Morus alba* (L) on 7, 12-dimethylbenz(a) Anthracene (DMBA) Induced buccal pouch Carcinoma in Syrian hamster, *Mesocricetus auratus* (L) *Int J Recent Sci*

- Res.*, 2015; 6: 3156-3161. [[Journal website](#)]
20. This study was also published:
21. Khyade VB, Mundhe SM, Syed S.A. Influence of Ethanolic Extractives of Leaves of Mulberry, *Morus alba* (L) On 7, 12-Dimethylbenz (A) Anthracene (DMBA) Induced Buccal Pouch Carcinoma in Syrian Hamster, *Mesocricetus auratus* (L). *IOSR J Pharm Biol Sci.*, 2015; 10: 69-75. [[Journal website](#)]
22. Kujawska M, Ewertowska M, Adamska T, Ignatowicz E, Flaczyk E, Przeor M, Kurpik M, Liebert JJ. Protective Effect of *Morus alba* Leaf Extract on N-Nitrosodiethylamine-induced Hepatocarcinogenesis in Rats. *In Vivo.*, 2016; 30: 807-812. DOI: 10.21873/invivo.10998
23. Fallah, S, Hajihassan Z, Sadeghi A. Cytotoxicity effects of flavonoid extract of *Morus alba* leaves in Hela cell line. *Asian J Biol Sci.*, 2017; 10: 72-79. DOI: 10.3923/ajbs.2017.72.79
24. Ramadan EM, Abou-Taleb KA, Galal GF, Abdel-Hamid NS. Antibacterial, antibiofilm and antitumor activities of grape and mulberry leaves ethanolic extracts towards bacterial clinical strains. *Ann Agric Sci.*, 2017; 62: 151-159. DOI: 10.1016/j.aos.2017.11.002
25. Min TR, Park HJ, Park MN, Kim B, Park SH. The Root Bark of *Morus alba* L. Suppressed the Migration of Human Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer Cells through Inhibition of Epithelial-Mesenchymal Transition Mediated by STAT3 and Src. *Int J Mol Sci.*, 2019; 20: 2244. DOI: 10.3390/ijms20092244
26. Yang MY, Wu CH, Hung TW, Wang CJ. Endoplasmic Reticulum Stress-Induced Resistance to Doxorubicin Is Reversed by Mulberry Leaf Polyphenol Extract in Hepatocellular Carcinoma through Inhibition of COX-2. *Antioxidants*, 2019; 9: 26. DOI: 10.3390/antiox9010026
27. Ghavami G, Muhammadnejad S, Amanpour S, Sardari S. Bioactivity Screening of Mulberry Leaf Extracts and two Related Flavonoids in Combination with Cisplatin on Human Gastric Adenocarcinoma Cells. *Iran J Pharm Res.*, 2020; 19: 371-382. DOI: 10.22037/ijpr.2020.1101087
28. Park HJ, Chi GY, Choi YH, Park SH. The root bark of *Morus alba* L. regulates tumor-associated macrophages by blocking recruitment and M2 polarization of macrophages. *Phytother Res.*, 2020; 34: 3333-3344. DOI: 10.1002/ptr.6783
29. Park SH, Park HJ. Root Bark extract of *Morus alba* L. Suppressed the Migration and Invasion of HCT116 Human Colorectal Carcinoma Cells. *J Physiol Pathol Korean Med.*, 2021; 35: 177-184. DOI: 10.15188/kjopp.2021.10.35.5.177

30. Mehreen Sadaf H, Bibi Y, Arshad M, Razzaq A, Ahmad S, Iriti M, Qayyum A. Analysis of *Peganum harmala*, *Melia azedarach* and *Morus alba* extracts against six lethal human cancer cells and oxidative stress along with chemical characterization through advance Fourier Transform and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance spectroscopic methods towards green chemotherapeutic agents. *Saudi Pharm J.*, 2021; 29: 552-565. DOI: 10.1016/j.jsps.2021.04.016
31. Chang YC, Wang CJ, Lai CJ, Huang HP. Mulberry fruit extract prevents liver fibrosis via inhibition of inflammation in DEN-treated rats. *Chung Shan Med J.*, 2021; 32: 1-10. [[Journal website](#)]
32. Abdel-Khalek HH, Mattar ZA. Biological activities of Egyptian grape and mulberry by-products and their potential use as natural sources of food additives and nutraceuticals foods. *J Food Meas Charact*, 2022; 16: 1559-1571. DOI: 10.1007/s11694-022-01289-2
33. Park HJ, Park SH. Root Bark of *Morus Alba L.* Induced p53-Independent Apoptosis in Human Colorectal Cancer Cells by Suppression of STAT3 Activity. *Nutr Cancer*, 2022; 74: 1837-1848. DOI: 10.1080/01635581.2021.1968444
34. Wakame K, Sato K, Kasai M, Kikuchi E, Shimizu K, Kudo A, Komatsu KI, Nakata A. Oral Administration of Mulberry (*Morus alba L.*) Leaf Powder Prevents the Development of Hepatocellular Carcinoma in Stelic Animal Model (STAM) Mice. *Anticancer Res.*, 2022; 42: 4055-4062. DOI: 10.21873/anticancer.15902
35. Chen C, Mokhtar RA, Kamaruzaman KA, Wei GT, Izzreen M.N. The cytotoxicity activity of Borneo-cultivated mulberry against breast cancer cell (MCF-7): the influence of maturity stages and extraction solvents. *Food Res.*, 2023; 7: 54-63. DOI: 10.26656/fr.2017.7(6).519
36. Lim SS, Mohd-Naim NF, Kifli N, Ming LC, Diah S. Investigating the anti-cancer potential of *Morus alba L.* extracts obtained from Brunei Darussalam on leukaemia cancer cells. *J Res Pharm.*, 2024; 28: 923-939. DOI: 10.29228/jrp.776
37. Srisomsap C, Chaisuriya P, Liana D, Aiyarakanchanakun P, Audsasan T, Weeraphan C, Svasti J, Phanumartwiwath A. Pharmacological Properties of White Mulberry (*Morus alba L.*) Leaves: Suppressing Migratory and Invasive Activities Against A549 Lung Cancer Cells. *Plant Foods Hum Nutr.*, 2024; 79: 387-393. DOI: 10.1007/s11130-024-01184-9
38. Ozaybi NA, Almasoudi SE, Bayomy HM, El-Ezaly FM. Anticancer potential of nanoemulsion-treated white mulberry and its leaves on MCF-7 cells. *Sci Rep.*, 2025; 15: 45550. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-025-29733-5

39. Kizi, T. *In vitro* anticancer and apoptotic effects of *Morus alba* L. leaf extract on human colorectal carcinoma (HCT-116) cell lines. *Int J Med Sci.*, 2025; 5: 310-315. [[Journal website](#)]
40. Yusupovna M, Kizi, T. New prospects of Walnut and Mulberry leaf extracts in oncology therapy. *Int J Med Sci.*, 2025; 5: 540-543. [[Journal website](#)]
41. Sargara P, Nataraj M, Subramanian RB, Thakkar AB. Hydromethanolic extracts of *Morus alba* L. (Mulberry) young and ripe fruit induces apoptosis in lung carcinoma cells (A549). *Braz J Pharm Sci.*, 2025; 61: e24112. DOI: 10.1590/s2175-97902025e24112
42. Liao SF, Liu JH, Xu M, Zheng JG. Evaluation of the Liver Cancer Prevention of Anthocyanin Extracts from Mulberry (*Morus alba* L.) Variety PR-01. *Adv Biosci Biotechnol*, 2018; 9: 423-442. DOI: 10.4236/abb.2018.99030
43. Long HL, Zhang FF, Wang HL, Yang WS, Hou HT, Yu JK, Liu B. Mulberry anthocyanins improves thyroid cancer progression mainly by inducing apoptosis and autophagy cell death. *Kaohsiung J Med Sci.*, 2018; 34: 255-262. DOI: 10.1016/j.kjms.2017.11.004
44. Nistor M, Ghiman R, Ayvaz H, Rugina D, Mada D, Stanila A, Socaciu C, Diaconeasa Z. 2018. Antiproliferative activity of anthocyanins pure extracts from mulberries and raspberries on HeLa and A2780 human cancer cell lines. *Bull UASVM Food Sci Technol.*, 2018; 75. DOI: 10.15835/buasvmcn-fst: 2017.0038
45. Li M, Wu X, Wang X, Shen T, Ren D. Two novel compounds from the root bark of *Morus alba* L. *Nat Prod Res.*, 2018; 32: 36-42. DOI: 10.1080/14786419.2017.1327862
46. Kollar P, Bárta T, Hošek J, Souček K, Závalová VM, Artinian S, Talhouk R, Smejkal K, Suchý P Jr, Hampl A. Prenylated Flavonoids from *Morus alba* L. Cause Inhibition of G1/S Transition in THP-1 Human Leukemia Cells and Prevent the Lipopolysaccharide-Induced Inflammatory Response. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med.*, 2013; 350519. DOI: 10.1155/2013/350519
47. Eo HJ, Park JH, Park GH, Lee MH, Lee JR, Koo JS, Jeong JB. Anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer activity of mulberry (*Morus alba* L.) root bark. *BMC Complement Altern Med.*, 2014; 14: 200. DOI: 10.1186/1472-6882-14-200
48. Bae MJ, Ye EJ. Antioxidant Activity and *in vitro* for Anticancer Effects of Manufactured Fermented Mulberry Leaf Tea. *J Korean Soc Food Sci Nutr.*, 2010; 39: 796-804. DOI: 10.3746/jkfn.2010.39.6.796 [Article in Korean]
49. Alam AK, Hossain AS, Khan MA, Kabir SR, Reza MA, Rahman MM, Islam MS, Rahman MA, Rashid M, Sadik MG. The Antioxidative Fraction of White Mulberry

- Induces Apoptosis through Regulation of p53 and NFκB in EAC Cells. *PLoS One.*, 2016; *11*: e0167536. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0167536
50. Burhan A, Awaluddin A, Zulham BT, Gafur A. Antioxidant and anticancer activities of murbei (*Morus alba* L.) stem extract on in vitro WiDr cancer cells. *J Farm Sains Dan Komun*, 2019; *16*: 63-67. DOI: 10.24071/jpsc.001698
51. Yang TY, Wu YL, Yu MH, Hung TW, Chan KC, Wang CJ. Mulberry Leaf and Neochlorogenic Acid Alleviates Glucolipotoxicity-Induced Oxidative Stress and Inhibits Proliferation/Migration via Downregulating Ras and FAK Signaling Pathway in Vascular Smooth Muscle Cell. *Nutrients*, 2022; *14*: 3006. DOI: 10.3390/nu14153006
52. Khyade VB, Sancer A. Treating the 7, 12-dimethylbenz (a) anthracene (DMBA) induced buccal pouch carcinoma in Syrian hamster, *Mesocricetus auratus* (L) with ethanolic extractives of leaves of mulberry, *Morus alba* (L). *World Sci. News.*, 2016; *30*: 1-13. [Journal Website]
53. Fallah S, Karimi A, Panahi G, Gerayesh Nejad S, Fadaei R, Seifi M. Human colon cancer HT-29 cell death responses to doxorubicin and *Morus alba* leaves flavonoid extract. *Cell Mol Biol.*, 2016; *62*: 72-77. DOI: 10.14715/cmb/2016.62.3.12
54. Dabili S, Fallah S, Aein M, Vatannejad A, Panahi G, Fadaei R, Moradi N, Shojaii A. Survey of the effect of doxorubicin and flavonoid extract of white *Morus alba* leaf on apoptosis induction in a-172 GBM cell line. *Arch Physiol Biochem*, 2019; *125*: 136-141. DOI: 10.1080/13813455.2018.1441871
55. Hisayoshi K, Masashi Y, Doi N, Koichi S. A novel cytotoxic prenylated flavonoid from the root of *Morus alba*. *J Insect Biotechnol Sericol*, 2004; *73*: 113-116. DOI: 10.11416/jibs.73.113
56. Yang Y1, Wang HQ, Chen RY. Flavonoids from the leaves of *Morus alba* L. *Acta Pharm Sin.*, 2010; *45*: 77-81. [ResearchGate, article in Chinese]
57. Fallah S, Hajihassan Z, Zarkar N, Chadegani AR, Mohammadnejad J, Hajimirzamohammad, M. Evaluation of anticancer activity of extracted flavonoids from *Morus alba* leaves and its interaction with DNA. *Braz Arch Biol Technol*, 2018; *61*: e16160623. DOI: 10.190/1678-4324-2018160623
58. Yu JS, Lee D, Lee SR, Lee JW, Choi CI, Jang TS, Kang KS, Kim KH. Chemical characterization of cytotoxic indole acetic acid derivative from mulberry fruit (*Morus alba* L.) against human cervical cancer. *Bioorg Chem.*, 2018; *76*: 28-36. DOI: 10.1016/j.bioorg.2017.10.015
59. Ma M, Luan X, Zheng H, Wang X, Wang S, Shen T, Ren D. A Mulberry Diels-Alder-

- Type Adduct, Kuwanon M, Triggers Apoptosis and Paraptosis of Lung Cancer Cells through Inducing Endoplasmic Reticulum Stress. *Int J Mol Sci.*, 2023; 24: 1015. DOI: 10.3390/ijms24021015
60. Deepa M, Sureshkumar T, Satheeshkumar PK, Priya S. Purified mulberry leaf lectin (MLL) induces apoptosis and cell cycle arrest in human breast cancer and colon cancer cells. *Chem Biol Interact*, 2012; 200: 38-44. DOI: 10.1016/j.cbi.2012.08.025
61. Deepa M, Priya S. Purification and characterization of a novel anti-proliferative lectin from *Morus alba* L. leaves. *Prot Pept Lett.*, 2012; 19: 839-845. DOI: 10.2174/092986612801619516
62. Saranya J, Shilpa G, Raghu KG, Priya S. *Morus alba* Leaf Lectin (MLL) Sensitizes MCF-7 Cells to Anoikis by Inhibiting Fibronectin Mediated Integrin-FAK Signaling through Ras and Activation of P38 MAPK. *Front. Pharmacol*, 2017; 8: 34. DOI: 10.3389/fphar.2017.00034
63. Kollar P, Bárta T, Keltošová S, Trnová P, Müller Závalová V, Šmejkal K, Hošek J, Fedr R, Souček K, Hampl A. Flavonoid 4'-O-Methylkuwanon E from *Morus alba* Induces the Differentiation of THP-1 Human Leukemia Cells. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med.*, 2015; 251895. DOI: 10.1155/2015/251895
64. Lim SL, Park SY, Kang S, Park D, Kim SH, Um JY, Jang HJ, Lee JH, Jeong CH, Jang JH, Ahn KS, Lee SG. Morusin induces cell death through inactivating STAT3 signaling in prostate cancer cells. *Am J Cancer Res.*, 2014; 5: 289-299. [PMC4300697]
65. Kang S, Kim EO, Kim SH, Lee JH, Ahn KS, Yun M, Lee SG. Morusin induces apoptosis by regulating expression of Bax and Survivin in human breast cancer cells. *Oncol Lett.*, 2017; 13: 4558-4562. DOI: 10.3892/ol.2017.6006
66. Park HJ, Min TR, Chi GY, Choi YH, Park SH. Induction of apoptosis by morusin in human non-small cell lung cancer cells by suppression of EGFR/STAT3 activation. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*, 2018; 505: 194-200. DOI: 10.1016/j.bbrc.2018.09.085
67. Liu S, Zhang J, Cao Z, Zhang H, Li X, Zhang S. Determination of Mulberroside A in Ramulus Mori extract and its antitumor effect in HepA tumor-bearing mice. *Biomed Res.*, 2017; 28: 3344-3349. [Journal website]
68. Chen NC, Chyau CC, Lee YJ, Tseng HC, Chou FP. Promotion of mitotic catastrophe via activation of PTEN by paclitaxel with supplement of mulberry water extract in bladder cancer cells. *Sci Rep.*, 2016; 6: 20417. DOI: 10.1038/srep20417
69. Xiaoman Z, Wenfeng L, Qifei C, Qun D, Kan, D. Isolation and structural characterization of the polysaccharides of cortex mori radices. *Acta Chim Sin.*, 2013; 71: 722-728. DOI:

- 10.6023/A13010109 [Article in Chinese]
70. Cui L, Lee HS, Oh WK, Ahn JS. Inhibition of Sanggenon G isolated from *Morus alba* on the metastasis of cancer cells. *Chin Herb Med.*, 2011; 3: 23-26. DOI: 10.3969/j.issn.1674-6384.2011.01.006
71. Hu X, Li J, Yu L, Ifejola J, Guo Y, Zhang D, Khosravi Z, Zhang K, Cui H. Screening of anti-melanoma compounds from *Morus alba* L.: Sanggenon C promotes melanoma cell apoptosis by disrupting intracellular Ca^{2+} homeostasis. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 2024; 324: 117759. DOI: 10.1016/j.jep.2024
72. Qian Z, Wu Z, Huang L, Qiu H, Wang L, Li L, Yao L, Kang K, Qu J, Wu Y, Luo J, Liu JJ, Yang Y, Yang W, Gou D. Mulberry fruit prevents LPS-induced NF- κ B/pERK/MAPK signals in macrophages and suppresses acute colitis and colorectal tumorigenesis in mice. *Sci Rep.*, 2015; 5: 17348. DOI: 10.1038/srep17348
73. Bayazid AB, Kim JG, Park SH, Lim BO. Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antiproliferative activity of Mori Cortex Radicis extracts. *Nat Prod Commun*, 2020; 15: 1-8. DOI: 10.1177/1934578X19899765
74. Li C, Peng Y, Tang W, Li T, Gatasheh MK, Rasheed RA, Fu J, He J, Wang WD, Shen Y, Yang Y. Antioxidant, anti-lipidemic, hypoglycemic and antiproliferative effects of phenolics from Cortex Mori Radicis. *Arab J Chem.*, 2022; 15: 103824. DOI: 10.1016/j.arabjc.2022.103824
75. Chon SU, Kim YM, Park YJ, Heo BG, Park YS, Gorinstein S. Antioxidant and antiproliferative effects of methanol extracts from raw and fermented parts of mulberry plant (*Morus alba* L.). *Eur Food Res Technol*, 2009; 230: 231-237. DOI: 10.1007/s00217-009-1165-2
76. Li F, Zhang B, Chen G, Fu X. Analysis of solvent effects on polyphenols profile, antiproliferative and antioxidant activities of mulberry (*Morus alba* L.) extracts. *Int J Food Sci Technol*, 2017; 52: 1690-1698. DOI: 10.1111/ijfs.13443
77. Fathy SA, Singab AN, Agwa SA, El Hamid DM, Zahra FA, El Moneim SM. The antiproliferative effect of mulberry (*Morus alba* L.) plant on hepatocarcinoma cell line HepG2. *Egypt J Med Hum Genet.*, 2013; 14: 375-382. DOI: 10.1016/j.ejmhg.2013.07.001
78. Yang Y, Yang X, Xu B, Zeng G, Tan J, He X, Hu C, Zhou Y. Chemical constituents of *Morus alba* L. and their inhibitory effect on 3T3-L1 preadipocyte proliferation and differentiation. *Fitoterapia*, 2014; 98: 222-227. DOI: 10.1016/j.fitote.2014.08.010
79. Soltanian S, Sheikhabahaei M, Mohamadi N. Cytotoxicity Evaluation of Methanol Extracts of Some Medicinal Plants on P19 Embryonal Carcinoma Cells. *J App Pharm*

- Sci.*, 2017; 7: 142-149. DOI: 10.7324/JAPS.2017.70722
80. Soni R, Gupta D, Gupte S, Rathour A, Shrivastava S, Shukla S. Phytochemical Screening and Evaluation of Antioxidant and Antiproliferative Potential of *Morus alba* (L.) Leaves Extracts Against Breast Cancer Cell Lines. *Toxicol Int.*, 2023; 30: 343–352. DOI: 10.18311/ti/2023/v30i3/33811
81. Zhang M, Wang RR, Cen M, Zhang HQ, Sun S, Zhang LY. A new flavanone glycoside with anti-proliferation activity from the root bark of *Morus alba*. *Chin J Nat Med.*, 2009; 7: 105-107. DOI: 10.1016/S1875-5364(09)60046-7
82. Song GR, Choi YJ, Park SJ, Shin S, Lee G, Choi HJ, Lee DY, Song GY, Oh S. Root Bark of *Morus alba* L. and Its Bioactive Ingredient, Ursolic Acid, Suppress the Proliferation of Multiple Myeloma Cells by Inhibiting Wnt/ β -Catenin Pathway. *J Microbiol Biotechnol*, 2021; 31: 1559-1567. DOI: 10.4014/jmb.2109.09002
83. Huang H, Liu N, Zhao K, Zhu C, Lu X, Li S, Lian W, Zhou P, Dong X, Zhao C, Guo H, Zhang C, Yang C, Wen G, Lu L, Li X, Guan L, Liu C, Wang X, Dou QP, Liu J. Sanggenon C decreases tumor cell viability associated with proteasome inhibition. *Front Biosci*, 2011; 3: 1315-1325. DOI: 10.2741/E335
84. Chang BY, Kim SB, Lee MK, Park H, Kim SY. Improved Chemotherapeutic Activity by *Morus alba* Fruits through Immune Response of Toll-Like Receptor 4. *Int J Mol Sci.*, 2015; 16: 24139-24158. DOI: 10.3390/ijms161024139
85. Dat NT, Binh PT, Quynh le TP, Van Minh C, Huong HT, Lee JJ. Cytotoxic prenylated flavonoids from *Morus alba*. *Fitoterapia*, 2010; 81: 1224-1227. DOI: 10.1016/j.fitote.2010.08.006
86. Qin J, Fan M, He J, Wu XD, Peng LY, Su J, Cheng X, Li Y, Kong LM, Li RT, Zhao QS. New cytotoxic and anti-inflammatory compounds isolated from *Morus alba* L. *Nat Prod Res.*, 2015; 29: 1711-1718. DOI: 10.1080/14786419.2014.999333
87. Yang Y, Zhang T, Xiao L, Yang L, Chen R. Two new chalcones from leaves of *Morus alba* L. *Fitoterapia*, 2010; 81: 614-616. DOI: 10.1016/j.fitote.2010.03.005
88. Kikuchi T, Nihei M, Nagai H, Fukushi H, Tabata K, Suzuki T, Akihisa T. Albanol A from the root bark of *Morus alba* L. induces apoptotic cell death in HL60 human leukemia cell line. *Chem Pharm Bull.*, 2010; 58: 568-571. DOI: 10.1248/cpb.58.568
89. Phan TN, Kim O, Ha MT, Hwangbo C, Min BS, Lee JH. Albanol B from Mulberries Exerts Anti-Cancer Effect through Mitochondria ROS Production in Lung Cancer Cells and Suppresses In Vivo Tumor Growth. *Int J Mol Sci.*, 2020; 21: 9502. DOI: 10.3390/ijms21249502

90. Cho E, Chung EY, Jang HY, Hong OY, Chae HS, Jeong YJ, Kim SY, Kim BS, Yoo DJ, Kim JS, Park KH. Anti-cancer Effect of Cyanidin-3-glucoside from Mulberry via Caspase-3 Cleavage and DNA Fragmentation in vitro and in vivo. *Anticancer Agents Med Chem.*, 2017; 17: 1519-1525. DOI: 10.2174/1871520617666170327152026
91. Shuang E, Yamamoto K, Sakamoto Y, Mizowaki Y, Iwagaki Y, Kimura T, Nakagawa K, Miyazawa T, Tsuduki T. Intake of mulberry 1-deoxynojirimycin prevents colorectal cancer in mice. *J Clin Biochem Nutr.*, 2017; 61: 47-52. DOI: 10.3164/jcbtn.16-94
92. Shu YH, Yuan HH, Xu MT, Hong YT, Gao CC, Wu ZP, Han HT, Sun X, Gao RL, Yang SF, Li SX, Tian JK, Zhang JB. A novel Diels-Alder adduct of mulberry leaves exerts anticancer effect through autophagy-mediated cell death. *Acta Pharmacol Sin.*, 2021; 42: 780-790. DOI: 10.1038/s41401-020-0492-5
93. Su J, Thakur A, Pan G, Yan J, Gaurav I, Thakur S, Yang Z, Cili A. Zhang, K. *Morus alba* derived Kuwanon-A combined with 5-fluorouracil reduce tumor progression via synergistic activation of GADD153 in gastric cancer. *MedComm Oncol*, 2023; 2: e24. DOI:10.1002/mog2.24
94. Yuan G, Qian P, Chen L, He N. Kuwanon C Inhibits Tumor Cell Proliferation and Induces Apoptosis by Targeting Mitochondria and Endoplasmic Reticulum. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, 2024; 25: 8293. DOI: 10.3390/ijms25158293
95. Yoshizawa S, Suganuma M, Fujiki H, Fukai T, Nomura T, Sugimura, T. Morusin, isolated from root bark of *Morus alba* L., inhibits tumour promotion of teleocidin. *Phytother. Res.*, 1989; 3: 193-195. DOI: 10.1002/ptr.2650030508
96. Wan LZ, Ma B, Zhang YQ. Preparation of morusin from *Ramulus mori* and its effects on mice with transplanted H₂₂ hepatocarcinoma. *Biofactors*, 2014; 40: 636-645. DOI: 10.1002/biof.1191
97. Ding B, Lv Y, Zhang YQ. Anti-tumor effect of morusin from the branch bark of cultivated mulberry in Bel-7402 cells via the MAPK pathway. *RSC Adv.*, 2016; 6: 17396-17404. DOI: 10.1039/c5ra21321e
98. Gao L, Wang L, Sun Z, Li H, Wang Q, Yi C, Wang X. Morusin shows potent antitumor activity for human hepatocellular carcinoma in vitro and in vivo through apoptosis induction and angiogenesis inhibition. *Drug Des Devel Ther.*, 2017; 11: 1789-1802. DOI: 10.2147/DDDT.S138320
99. Yin XL, Lv Y, Wang S, Zhang YQ. Morusin suppresses A549 cell migration and induces cell apoptosis by downregulating the expression of COX-2 and VEGF genes. *Oncol Rep.*, 2018; 40: 504-510. DOI: 10.3892/or.2018.6431

100. Cho AR, Park WY, Lee HJ, Sim DY, Im E, Park JE, Ahn CH, Shim BS, Kim SH. Antitumor Effect of Morusin via G1 Arrest and Antiglycolysis by AMPK Activation in Hepatocellular Cancer. *Int J Mol Sci.*, 2021; 22: 10619. DOI: 10.3390/ijms221910619
101. Li H, Wang Q, Dong L, Liu C, Sun Z, Gao L, Wang X. Morusin suppresses breast cancer cell growth in vitro and in vivo through C/EBP β and PPAR γ mediated lipopapoptosis. *J Exp Clin Cancer Res.*, 2015; 34: 137. DOI: 10.1186/s13046-015-0252-4
102. Wu HE, Su CC, Wang SC, Liu PL, Cheng WC, Yeh HC, Chuu CP, Chen JK, Bao BY, Lee CH, Ke CC, Chen YR, Yu YH, Huang SP, Li CY. Anticancer Effects of Morusin in Prostate Cancer via Inhibition of Akt/mTOR Signaling Pathway. *Am J Chin Med.*, 2023; 51: 1019-1039. DOI: 10.1142/S0192415X23500477
103. Guo L, Dong Z, Zhang X, Yang Y, Hu X, Ji Y, Li C, Wan S, Xu J, Liu C, Zhang Y, Liu L, Shi Y, Wu Z, Liu Y, Cui H. Morusinol extracted from *Morus alba* induces cell cycle arrest and apoptosis via inhibition of DNA damage response in melanoma by CHK1 degradation through the ubiquitin-proteasome pathway. *Phytomedicine*, 2023; 114: 154765. DOI: 10.1016/j.phymed.2023.154765
104. Duan C, Han J, Zhang C, Wu K, Lin Y. Inhibition of kidney cancer cell growth by Mulberroside-A is mediated via mitochondrial mediated apoptosis, inhibition of cell migration and invasion and targeting EGFR signalling pathway. *J BUON.*, 2019; 24: 296-300. [Journal website]
105. Tang WH, Zhang ZN, Cai HR, Sun W, Yang H, Zhao EH, Cui HJ. Effect of *Morus alba* extract Sanggenon C on growth and proliferation of glioblastoma cells. *Zhongguo Zhong Yao Za Zhi.*, 2023; 48: 211-219. DOI: 10.19540/j.cnki.cjcm.20220905.701 [Article in Chinese]
106. Liu Y, Tang A, Liu M, Luo Z, Cao F, Yang C. The effectiveness of Sanggenon C in alleviating SLC7A11-induced ferroptosis in lung cancer was evaluated using in vivo, in vitro, and computational approaches. *Int Immunopharmacol*, 2025; 145: 113819. DOI: 10.1016/j.intimp.2024.113819
107. Li ZR, Ma T, Guo YJ, Hu B, Niu SH, Suo FZ, Du LN, You YH, Kang WT, Liu S, Mamun M, Song QM, Pang JR, Zheng YC, Liu HM. Sanggenon O induced apoptosis of A549 cells is counterbalanced by protective autophagy. *Bioorg Chem.*, 2019; 87: 688-698. DOI: 10.1016/j.bioorg.2019.03.072
108. Dat NT, Jin X, Lee K, Hong YS, Kim YH, Lee JJ. Hypoxia-inducible factor-1 inhibitory benzofurans and chalcone-derived diels-alder adducts from *Morus* species. *J*

- Nat Prod.*, 2009; 72: 39-43. DOI: 10.1021/np800491u
109. Kim HH, Park KH, Kim MH, Oh MH, Kim SR, Park KJ, Heo JH, Lee MW. Antiproliferative effects of native plants on prostate cancer cells. *Nat Prod Sci.*, 2013; 19: 192-200. [Journal website]
110. Rao SA, Ramesh CK, Mahmood R, Jamuna KS, Prabhakar, BT. Anti tumor activity of two species of Mulberry against eat cell lines in mice. *World J Pharm Res.*, 2015; 4: 1934-1943. [ResearchGate]
111. Rao SA, Mathad S, Jamuna KS, Chapeyil R. Characterization of isolated compounds from *Morus* spp. and their biological activity as anticancer molecules. *Bioimpacts*, 2021; 11: 187-197. DOI: 10.34172/bi.2021.09
112. Agabeyli RA. Antimutagenic Activities Extracts from Leaves of the *Morus alba*, *Morus nigra* and Their Mixtures. *Int J Biol.*, 2012; 4: 166-172. DOI: 10.5539/ijb.v4n2p166
113. El-Baz FK, Hassan AZ, Abd-Alla HI, Aly HF, Mahmoud K. Phytochemical analysis, assessment of antiproliferative and free radical scavenging activity of *Morus alba* and *Morus rubra* fruits. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.*, 2017; 10: 189-199. DOI: 10.22159/ajpcr.2017.v10i6.18029
114. Tseng TH, Chung WC, Lee W, Lee YJ. Morusin from *Morus australis* roots inhibits 12-O-tetradecanoylphorbol-13-acetate induced transformation of epidermal JB6 cells. *Biophys J.*, 2014; 106: 475a. DOI: 10.1016/j.bpj.2013.11.2686
115. Zhang QJ, Tang YB, Chen RY, Yu DQ. Three New Cytotoxic Diels–Alder-Type Adducts from *Morus australis*. *Chem Biodiver*, 2007; 4: 1533-1540. DOI: 10.1002/cbdv.200790133
116. Mihara S, Hara M, Nakamura M, Sakurawi K, Tokura K, Fujimoto M, Fukai T, Nomura T. Non-peptide bombesin receptor antagonists, kuwanon G and H, isolated from mulberry. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun.*, 1995; 213: 594-599. DOI: 10.1006/bbrc.1995.2173
117. Shen RC, Lin M. Diels-Alder type adducts from *Morus cathayana*. *Phytochemistry*, 2001; 57: 1231-1235. DOI: 10.1016/s0031-9422(01)00171-6
118. Viveros-Valdez E, Oranday-Cárdenas A, Rivas-Morales C, Verde-Star MJ, Carranza-Rosales P. Biological activities of *Morus celtidifolia* leaf extracts. *Pak J Pharm Sci.*, 2015; 28: 1177-1180. [ResearchGate]
119. Prasad L, Khan TH, Sehrawat A, Sultana S. Modulatory effect of *Morus indica* against two-stage skin carcinogenesis in Swiss albino mice: possible mechanism by inhibiting aryl hydrocarbon hydroxylase. *J Pharm Pharmacol*, 2004; 56: 1291-1298. DOI:

- 10.1211/0022357044373
120. Kotebagilu NP, Shivanna LM, Urooj A. Anti-Cancer Potential of *Morus indica* Hybrid Varieties in HT-29 Cancer Cell Lines: an Exploratory Study. *Int J Pharm Sci Res.*, 2021; 12: 587-596. DOI: 10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.12(1).587-96
121. Islam MS, Jahangir CA, Rahi MS, Hasan MM, Sajib SA, Hoque KMF, Reza MA. In-vivo antiproliferative activity of *Morus latifolia* leaf and bark extracts against Ehrlich's ascites carcinoma. *Toxicol Res.*, 2019; 36: 79-88. DOI: 10.1007/s43188-019-00011-7
122. Happyana N, Hakim EH, Syah YM, Kayser O, Juliawaty LD, Mujahidin D, Ermayanti TM, Achmad SA. Diels-Alder type adducts from hairy root cultures of *Morus macroura*. *Nat Prod Sci.*, 2019; 25: 233-237. DOI: 10.20307/nps.2019.25.3.233
123. Hamdan DI, Salah S, Hassan WH, Morsi M, Khalil HM, Ahmed-Farid OA, El-Shiekh RA, Nael MA, Elissawy AM. Anticancer and Neuroprotective Activities of Ethyl Acetate Fractions from *Morus macroura* Miq. Plant Organs with Ultrapformance Liquid Chromatography-Electrospray Ionization-Tandem Mass Spectrometry Profiling. *ACS Omega*, 2022; 7: 16013-16027. DOI: 10.1021/acsomega.2c01148
124. Liu W, Ji Y, Wang F, Li C, Shi S, Liu R, Li Q, Guo L, Liu Y, Cui H. Morusin shows potent antitumor activity for melanoma through apoptosis induction and proliferation inhibition. *BMC Cancer*, 2023; 23: 602. DOI: 10.1186/s12885-023-11080-1
125. Zelefack F, Guilet D, Valentin A, Fongang R, Kom B, Chevalley S, Ngouela S, Tsamo E, Fabre N, Dijoux-Franca, MG. Antiplasmodial and cytotoxic activities of flavonoids and arylbenzofuran derivatives from *Morus mesozygia*. *Greener J Biol Sci.*, 2012; 2: 20-24. DOI: 10.15580/GJBS.2012.2.08241250
126. Sindhu T, Rajamanikandan S, Durgapriya D, Anitha JR, Akila S, Gopalakrishnan VK. Molecular docking and QSAR studies on plant derived bioactive compounds as potent inhibitors of DEK oncoprotein. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.*, 2011; 4: 67-71. [ResearchGate]
127. Shi YQ, Fukai T, Sakagami H, Chang WJ, Yang PQ, Wang FP, Nomura T. Cytotoxic flavonoids with isoprenoid groups from *Morus mongolica*. *J Nat Prod.*, 2001; 64: 181-188. DOI: 10.1021/np000317c
128. Qadir MI, Ali M, Ibrahim Z. Anti-cancer activity of *Morus nigra* leaves extract. *Bangladesh J Pharmacol*, 2014; 9: 496-497. DOI: 10.3329/bjp.v9i4.19783
129. Ahmed A, Ali M, El-Kholie E, El-Garawani I, Sherif N. Anticancer activity of *Morus nigra* on human breast cancer cell line (MCF-7): the role of fresh and dry fruit extracts. *J Biosci Appl Res.*, 2016; 2: 352-361. [ResearchGate]

130. Cakıroğlu E, Uysal T, Kocal GC, Aygenli F, Baran G, Baskın Y. The Role of *Morus nigra* Extract and Its Active Compounds as Drug Candidate on Human Colorectal Adenocarcinoma Cell Line HT-29. *Int J Clin Oncol Cancer Res.*, 2017; 2: 10-14. DOI: 10.11648/j.ijcocr.20170201.13
131. Yilmaz S, Ucar A, Goktas B. Genotoxic and Genoprotective Potential of Black Mulberry (*Morus nigra*) Fruit. *An Acad Bras Cienc*, 2019; 91: e20190337. DOI: 10.1590/0001-3765201920190337
132. Roussos PA, Denaxa NK, Ntanos E, Tsafouros A, Mavrikou S, Kintzios S. Organoleptic, nutritional and anti-carcinogenic characteristics of the fruit and rooting performance of cuttings of black mulberry (*Morus nigra* L.) genotypes. *J Berry Res.*, 2020; 10: 77-93. DOI: 10.3233/JBR-190422
133. Hooshmand S, Mahdinezhad MR, Taraz Jamshidi S, Soukhtanloo M, Mirzavi F, Iranshahi M, Hasanpour M, Ghorbani A. *Morus nigra* L. extract prolongs survival of rats with hepatocellular carcinoma. *Phytother Res.*, 2021; 35: 3365-3376. DOI: 10.1002/ptr.7056
134. Dalkiliç S, Dalkiliç IK, İnci, S, Korkmaz I, Kırbağ S. Investigation of cytotoxic effect of black mulberry (*Morus nigra* L.) fruit. *Indian J Trad Knowl*, 2021; 20: 54-58. [[ResearchGate](#)]
135. Erden Y. Sour black mulberry (*Morus nigra* L.) causes cell death by decreasing mutant 53. expression in HT-29 human colon cancer cells. *Food Biosci*, 2021; 42: 101113. DOI: 10.1016/J.FBIO.2021.101113
136. Almutairi BO, Alsayadi AI, Abutaha N, Al-Mekhlafi FA, Wadaan MA. Evaluation of the Anticancer Potential of *Morus nigra* and *Ocimum basilicum* Mixture against Different Cancer Cell Lines: An In Vitro Evaluation. *Biomed Res Int.*, 2023; 9337763. DOI: 10.1155/2023/9337763
137. Cui WS, Zhang Q, Zhao XH. Impact of heat treatment on anti-oxidative and anti-colon cancer activities of the soluble extracts from black mulberry (*Morus nigra* L.) using water and ethanol-water solvents. *RSC Adv.*, 2020; 10: 30415-30427. DOI: 10.1039/d0ra05598k
138. Wang Y, Zheng M, Jiang Q, Xu Y, Zhou X, Zhang N, Sun D, Li H, Chen L. Chemical Components of the Fruits of *Morus nigra* Linn.: Methyl Caffeate as a Potential Anticancer Agent by Targeting 3-Phosphoglycerate Dehydrogenase. *J Agric Food Chem.*, 2021; 69: 12433-12444. DOI: 10.1021/acs.jafc.1c03215
139. Gao Q, Chen N, Li B, Zu M, Ya Ma Y, Xu H, Zhu Z, Reis RL, Kundu SC, Xiao B.

- Natural lipid nanoparticles extracted from *Morus nigra* L. leaves for targeted treatment of hepatocellular carcinoma via the oral route. *J Nanobiotechnol*, 2024; 22: 4. DOI: 10.1186/s12951-023-02286-3
140. Turan I, Demir S, Kilinc K, Burnaz NA, Yaman SO, Akbulut K, Mentese A, Aliyazicioglu Y, Deger O. Antiproliferative and apoptotic effect of *Morus nigra* extract on human prostate cancer cells. *Saudi Pharm J.*, 2017; 25: 241-248. DOI: 10.1016/j.jsps.2016.06.002
141. Abdel Bar FM, Abbas GM, Gohar AA, Lahloub MI. Antiproliferative activity of stilbene derivatives and other constituents from the stem bark of *Morus nigra* L. *Nat Prod Res.*, 2020; 34: 3506-3513. DOI: 10.1080/14786419.2019.1573236
142. Ferlinahayati F, Syah YM, Juliawaty LD, Hakim EH. Flavanones from the Wood of *Morus nigra* with Cytotoxic Activity. *Indones J Chem.*, 2013; 13: 205-208. DOI: 10.22146/ijc.21277
143. Patharakorn T, Arpornsuwan T, Wetprasit N, Promboon A, Ratanapo S. Antibacterial activity and cytotoxicity of the leaf essential oil of *Morus rotundiloba* Koidz. *J Med Plants Res.*, 2010; 4: 837-843. DOI: 10.5897/JMPR10.131
144. Patharakorn T, Talawat S, Promboon A, Wetprasit N, Ratanapo S. Antimutagenicity and anti-HSV-2 activity of mulberry tea (*Morus rotundiloba* Koidz). *Agric Nat Resour*, 2010; 44: 816-823. [ResearchGate]
145. Demir S, Turan I, Aliyazicioglu Y, Kilinc K, Yaman SO, Ayazoglu Demir E, Arslan A, Mentese A, Deger O. *Morus Rubra* Extract Induces Cell Cycle Arrest and Apoptosis in Human Colon Cancer Cells Through Endoplasmic Reticulum Stress and Telomerase. *Nutr Cancer.*, 2017; 69: 74-83. DOI: 10.1080/01635581.2017.1247887
146. Turan I, Demir S, Kilinc K, Aliyazicioglu Y, Alver A, Misir S, Ozer Yaman S, Akbulut K, Mentese A, Orhan Deger O. *Morus rubra* Extract Induces G₁ Cell Cycle Arrest and Apoptosis in Human Lung and Prostate Cancer Cells. *Indian J Pharm Edu Res.*, 2017; 51: 51-58. DOI: 10.5530/ijper.51.1.8
147. Tan Y, Liu C, Chen R. Phenolic constituents from stem bark of *Morus wittiorum* and their antiinflammation and cytotoxicity. *China J Chin Mater Med.*, 2010; 35: 2700-2702. DOI: 10.4268/cjcm20102013 [Article in Chinese]
148. Tan YX, Wang HQ, Chen RY. Anti-inflammatory and cytotoxic 2-arylbenzofurans from *Morus wittiorum*. *Fitoterapia*, 2012; 83: 750-753. DOI: 10.1016/j.fitote.2012.03.001
149. Tan YX, Liu C, Zhang T, Chen RY, Yu DQ. Bioactive constituents of *Morus wittiorum*.

- Phytochem Lett.*, 2010; 3: 57-61. DOI: 10.1016/j.phytol.2009.11.006
150. Tan YX, Liu C, Chen RY. New 2-arylbenzofurans with selective cytotoxicity from *Morus wittiorum*. *Phytochem Lett.*, 2012; 5: 419-422. DOI: 10.1016/j.phytol.2012.03.012
151. Azab A. *Morus* Plant Genus: Superb Antidiabetic Activity and Outstanding Source of Nutrients. *J Biomed Res Environ Sci.*, 2023; 4: 806-832. DOI: 10.37871/jbres1739
152. Azab A. *Morus* (Mulberry) and Its Brain-Related Protective Activities. Literature Update. *World J. Pharm. Res.*, 2025; 14: 39-76. DOI: 10.20959/wjpr20259-36521
153. Azab A. Anti-Inflammatory Activity of *Morus* (Mulberry) Species. *World J. Pharm. Res.*, 2026; 15: 349-399. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18428141
154. Pratama AH, Fareza MS, Choironi NA, Sarmoko S. 2023, December. Bioinformatic study of the active compound of morin in mulberry (*Morus alba*) as breast anticancer. *AIP Conf. Proc.*, 2023; 2972. DOI: 10.1063/5.0184914
155. Fenderya S, Yazıcı Kaya ZI, Akdeniz V, Fırat E, Dinkçi N. Optimization of Different Methods for the Extraction of Mulberry Leaves and the Effects on Caco-2 Cells. *Processes*, 2026; 14: 31. DOI: 10.3390/pr14010031
156. Deshmukh SR, Habtemariam S, Wadegaonkar PA. Antioxidant and Antiproliferative Activity of Root Suspension Culture of *Morinda citrifolia* L. *Res J Pharm Technol.*, 2010; 3: 1189-1193. [Journal website]
157. Baran MF, Meşe A, Eftekhari A. *Morus alba* L. Leaves-Based Silver Nanoparticles for Aging-Related Infectious Diseases. *Int J Aging*, 2023; 1: e23. DOI: 10.34172/ija.2023.e23
158. Nazario-Naveda R, Delfin-Narciso D, Juárez-Cortijo L, Gallozzo-Cárdenas M, Angelats-Silva L. Eco-Friendly synthesis of silver nanoparticles via *Morus Nigra* extract in ethanol: A sustainable nanomaterial approach. *AIP Conf Proc.*, 2026; 3486. DOI: 10.1063/12.0042895
159. Minhas GF, Kiani BH, Ghani U, Ahmad KS, Shah A. Biogenic synthesis of nanosilver particles from root extract of *Morus alba* L. and their biological activities. *Farmacia*, 2021; 69: 90-99. DOI: 10.31925/farmacia.2021.1.12
160. Kumkoon T, Srisaisap M, Boonserm P. Biosynthesized Silver Nanoparticles Using *Morus alba* (White Mulberry) Leaf Extract as Potential Antibacterial and Anticancer Agents. *Molecules*, 2023; 28: 1213. DOI: 10.3390/molecules28031213
161. Kim HB, You HS, Ryu SJ, Lee HY, Baek JS. Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles from mulberry leaf through hot melt extrusion: Enhanced antioxidant, antibacterial,

- anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, and anticancer properties. *Food Hydrocoll Health*, 2024; 6: 100184. DOI: 10.1016/j.fhfh.2024.100184
162. Sarah J. Green Synthesis, Characterization, and Evaluation of the Biological Activities of Silver Nanoparticles Synthesized from *Morus indica* (Mulberry) Fruit Extract. *World J Pharm Pharm Sci.*, 2017; 6: 1283-1301. DOI: 10.20959/wjpps20176-9342
163. Some S, Bulut O, Biswas K, Kumar A, Roy A, Sen IK, Mandal A, Franco OL, İnce İA, Neog K, Das S, Pradhan S, Dutta S, Bhattacharjya D, Saha S, K, Mohapatra D, Bhuimali A, Unni BG, Kati A, Mandal AK, Deniz Yilmaz M. Ocsoy, I. Effect of feed supplementation with biosynthesized silver nanoparticles using leaf extract of *Morus indica* L. V1 on *Bombyx mori* L. (Lepidoptera: Bombycidae). *Sci Rep.*, 2019; 9: 14839. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-019-50906-6
164. Jeon YN, Ryu SJ, Lee HY, Kim JO, Baek JS. Green Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticle Using Black Mulberry and Characterization, Phytochemical, and Bioactivity. *Antibiotics*, 2024; 13: 686. DOI: 10.3390/antibiotics13080686
165. Akmeşe O, Baltacı C, Gültekin E, Taskın II, Sever MR, Derin DÇ, Karpuz Ö. Phytogetic Silver and Copper Nanoparticles from *Morus nigra* L. Leaf as Multifunctional Agents: Antioxidant, Antidiabetic, Antimicrobial, and Anticancer Potency. *Turkish J Analyt Chem.*, 2025; 7: 321-337. DOI: 10.51435/turkjac.1738363
166. Anjum S, Khan AK, Qamar A, Fatima N, Drouet S, Renouard S, Blondeau JP, Abbasi BH, Hano C. Light Tailoring: Impact of UV-C Irradiation on Biosynthesis, Physiognomies, and Clinical Activities of *Morus macroura*-Mediated Monometallic (Ag and ZnO) and Bimetallic (Ag-ZnO) Nanoparticles. *Int J Mol Sci.*, 2021; 22: 11294. DOI: 10.3390/ijms222011294
167. Sadeghi-Aliabadi H, Mirian M, Banizaman A, Rezazadeh M, Rahimi F, Sepahi S, Sadeghi-Aliabadi M. Gold nanoparticles from *Artemisia absinthium*, *Morus nigra*, and *Peganum harmala*: biosynthesis, characterization, and their biological evaluations against cancer cells. *Res Pharm Sci.*, 2025; 20: 485-497. DOI: 10.4103/RPS.RPS_159_23
168. Rocha LV, Lishanti R, Madeena Begum S, Hadsun Jona A, Rani JC. Phytosynthesis of Selenium Nanoparticles from *Morus rubra* (L.) and Evaluation of its Bioactive Potential: Antioxidant, Antimicrobial, and Anticancer. *Anticancer Agents Med Chem.*, 2026. DOI: 10.2174/0118715206428455251210203908 (In press)
169. Paranthaman S, Shivakumar CS, Kalaipriya S, Venkatesh HN, Giresha J, Pasha S, Shazly GA, Anandan S, Shivamallu C, Kollur SP. One-pot green synthesis of zinc

- oxide nanoparticles using *Morus laevigata* aqueous extract and evaluation of its anticancer potential against HT-29 cell line. *Main Group Metal Chem.*, 2024; 47: 20240016. DOI: 10.1515/mgmc-2024-0016
170. Tang Q, Xia H, Liang W, Huo X, Wei X. Synthesis and characterization of zinc oxide nanoparticles from *Morus nigra* and its anticancer activity of AGS gastric cancer cells. *J Photochem Photobiol B Biol.*, 2020; 202: 111698. DOI: 10.1016/j.jphotobiol.2019.111698
171. Cho SW, Na W, Choi M, Kang SJ, Lee SG, Choi CY. Autophagy inhibits cell death induced by the anti-cancer drug morusin. *Am J Cancer Res.*, 2017; 7: 518-530. [Journal Website]
172. Agarwal S, Mohamed MS, Raveendran S, Rochani AK, Maekawa T, Kumar DS. Formulation, characterization and evaluation of morusin loaded niosomes for potentiation of anticancer therapy. *RSC Adv.*, 2018; 8: 32621-32636. DOI: 10.1039/c8ra06362a
173. Park HJ, Park SH. Induction of cytoprotective autophagy by morusin via AMP-activated protein kinase activation in human non-small cell lung cancer cells. *Nutr Res Pract*, 2020; 14: 478-489. DOI: 10.4162/nrp.2020.14.5.478
174. Wang J, Liu X, Zheng H, Liu Q, Zhang H, Wang X, Shen T, Wang S, Ren D. Morusin induces apoptosis and autophagy via JNK, ERK and PI3K/Akt signaling in human lung carcinoma cells. *Chem Biol Interact*, 2020; 331: 109279. DOI: 10.1016/j.cbi.2020.109279
175. Bailly C. Anticancer mechanism of artonin E and related prenylated flavonoids from the medicinal plant *Artocarpus elasticus*. *Asian J Nat Prod Biochem*, 2021; 19: 45-57. DOI: 10.13057/biofar/f190202
176. Sarmoko S, Pratama AH, Choironi NA, Fareza MS. Bioinformatic Study of the Active Compound of Morusin in Mulberry (*Morus alba*) against Breast Cancer. *Indones J Cancer Chemoprevent*, 2023; 14: 60-71. DOI: 10.14499/indonesianjcanchemoprev14iss1pp60-71
177. Ran Y, Hu J, Chen Y, Rao Z, Zhao J, Xu Z, Ming J. Morusin-Cu(II)-indocyanine green nanoassembly ignites mitochondrial dysfunction for chemo-photothermal tumor therapy. *J Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2024; 662: 760-773. DOI: 10.1016/j.jcis.2024.02.121
178. Choi DW, Cho SW, Lee SG, Choi CY. The Beneficial Effects of Morusin, an Isoprene Flavonoid Isolated from the Root Bark of *Morus*. *Int J Mol Sci.*, 2020; 21: 6541. DOI: 10.3390/ijms21186541

179. Panek-Krzysko A, Stompor-Goracy M. The Pro-Health Benefits of Morusin Administration - An Update Review. *Nutrients*, 2021; 13: 3043. DOI: 10.3390/nu13093043
180. Hafeez A, Khan Z, Armaghan M, Khan K, Sönmez Güreç E, Abdull Razis AF, Modu B, Almarhoon ZM, Setzer WN, Sharifi-Rad J. Exploring the therapeutic and anti-tumor properties of Morusin: a review of recent advances. *Front Mol Biosci*, 2023; 10: 1168298. DOI: 10.3389/fmolb.2023.1168298
181. Fatima M, Dar MA, Dhanavade MJ, Abbas SZ, Bukhari MN, Arsalan A, Liao Y, Wan J, Bukhari J, Ouyang Z. Biosynthesis and Pharmacological Activities of the Bioactive Compounds of White Mulberry (*Morus alba*): Current Paradigms and Future Challenges. *Biology*, 2024; 13: 506. DOI: 10.3390/biology13070506
182. Chan EW. Chemistry and Pharmacology of Morusin and Morusinol from *Morus alba*: An Overview. *Trop J Nat Prod Res.*, 2025; 9: 904-911. DOI: 10.26538/tjnpr/v9i3.03
183. Zoofishan Z, Hohmann J, Hunyadi A. Phenolic antioxidants of *Morus nigra* roots, and antitumor potential of morusin. *Phytochem Rev.*, 2018; 17: 1031-1045. DOI: 10.1007/s11101-018-9565-1
184. Azzam HN, El-Dessouki AM, Attallah KA, Sadek MA, Aboulmagd YM, Hassan M-AM, Fahmy MI, El-Shiekh RA, Kamal RM, Khalifa HO. Morusin as a drug candidate: opportunities, limitations, and the path toward clinical translation. *Front. Pharmacol*, 2025; 16: 1704535. DOI: 10.3389/fphar.2025.1704535
185. Tseng TH, Chuang SK, Hu CC, Chang CF, Huang YC, Lin CW, Lee YJ. The synthesis of Morusin as a potent antitumor agent. *Tetrahedron*, 2010; 66: 1335-1340. DOI: 10.1016/j.tet.2009.12.002